

Deliverable 4.1

EOSC Registries for Research Data and Metadata Interoperability and Research Activity Tracking

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable serves to provide a technical account of the development work and the three services developed in work package 4: MSCR, DTR and RAiD. This deliverable also gives context for the work by showcasing the requirement collection and progress monitoring work. Finally, the demonstrators have shown the practical application context for the developed services. The deliverable draws out the full picture and provides more detail than is possible to give in a typical scientific paper, and the authors hope that this can serve as a point of reference in the future, for the work carried out in FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CAT	Compliance Assessment Toolkit
CERIF	The Common European Research Information Format
CSV	Comma Separated Values
DB	Database
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DTR	Data Type Registry
EduGAIN	EDUcation Global Authentication INfrastructure
ENUM	List of values.
EOSC	The European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAIRCORE4EOSC	Developing EOSC-Core components to enable a FAIR EOSC ecosystem
FTE	Full-time equivalent
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IT	Information Technology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON Schema	JSON based model for describing and validating JSON documents.
JSON-LD	JSON for Linking Data. Model for expressing RDF graphs in JSON.
LCPM	Lifecycle Product Management
MSCR	Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry
NREN	National research and education network
OS	Operating system
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PDF	Portable Document Format
PID	Persistent Identifier
PMB	Project Management Board
RAG	Retrieval-augmented Generation. Technique for allowing generative AI models to incorporate new information for example from knowledge graphs.
RAiD	Research Activity Identifier
RDF	Resource Description Framework. Model for labelled directed graphs.
RDFS	Resource Description Framework Schema. RDF based language for describing schemas.
RDM	Research Data Management
RegEx	Regular Expression
REST	Representational State Transfer
RML	RDF Mapping Language.
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language. Language and a protocol to implement authentication and authorisation.
SEMAF	Semantic Annotation Framework
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language. Language for describing and validating RDF graphs.
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SP	Service Point
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and Query Language. Query language for RDF graphs.
SSSOM	Simple Standard for Sharing Ontology Mappings
UI	User Interface

XSD	XML Schema Definition. XML based language for describing and validating XML documents.
XSLT	Extensible Stylesheet Language Transformations. XML based language for the transformation of XML documents.

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Executive Summary

In general, the FAIRCORE4EOSC project has planned to produce services, addressing gaps in FAIR according to the SRIA v1.0. The services that the project has developed are now produced and launched. Thus, the main contribution of the project to the future of the EOSC partnership is delivered. This deliverable serves to provide a technical account of the development work and the three services developed in work package 4: MSCR, DTR and RAiD. This deliverable also gives context for the work by showcasing the requirement collection and progress monitoring work. Finally, the demonstrators have shown the practical application context for the developed services. The deliverable draws out the full picture and provides more detail than is possible to give in a typical scientific paper, and the authors hope that this can serve as a point of reference in the future, for the work carried out in FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

The time span for the service development in FAIRCORE4EOSC was challenging. Getting the development teams working and a full spectrum of specifications by project month 8 was intensive. Having 10 months to develop the beta releases was even tougher. This was a necessary and planned step to allow for enough time for the case studies to adopt the work during the lifetime of the project. This turned out to be more challenging than thought, as the beta versions with limited functionality were not in all cases adequate to satisfy the more complex use cases of the case studies. The service development teams were then working with the case studies during the next 16 months to prioritise and ensure that the development efforts toward the final releases of the services fulfilled the case study and other stakeholders needs. The project had an overall KPI for satisfying at least 80% of the accepted user requirements (for all services), and this KPI was met. The requirements were consistently monitored and refined as the implementation work progressed. The task 4.1 documented in this deliverable played a big mobilising role for requirement management for the entire project. Follow up of the progress in meeting the requirements was a recurring point on the agenda of project meetings. Likewise, T4.5 on the demonstrators was the in practice a project wide beacon for demonstrator work.

Significant effort also went into disseminating the development work, and WP4 was very active in this regard. For the first 18 months the communication was related to aligning efforts between different EOSC and non EOSC-actors, talking essentially about what was planned to be done. This served to raise interest in adoption. After the release of the beta versions, the focus gradually shifted to showcasing the developed services. Especially for the MSCR, users are lining up, showcasing the real need for the service in the science communities.

1 Introduction

FAIRCORE4EOSC¹, funded by the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, is a project contributing to the co-programmed European Partnership on the European Open Science Cloud. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a flagship EU initiative to deepen Open Science practices across the European Research Area (ERA). As such it contributes to several actions of the ERA policy agenda (European Commission, 2022). EOSC is also recognised in the European strategy for data as the data space for science, research and innovation to be fully aligned with the other sectoral data spaces defined in the strategy (A European Strategy for Data, 2020).

As a Research and Innovation Action (RIA), FAIRCORE4EOSC developed nine new EOSC-Core components to support a FAIR EOSC and to enhance interoperability and discoverability of research outputs. Development activities of the components (WP2-6) are carried out by utilising existing services and technologies, as far as possible. To ensure that testing and development of the components is driven by user needs, the project has identified five user-centric case studies (WP7), documented in the “D7.2 Report on the Release of Case Studies” (Elbers et al., 2025). The case studies also act as early adopters of the components in the communities they represent. While the case studies focus on immediate community benefit and integrating several new services, the demonstrator tasks in the work packages (e.g. T4.5) focus on demonstrating the utility of individual services in direct interaction with the service developers within the WP. This deliverable is the final report summarising the service development activities carried out in WP4 and documenting the production release of the components.

FAIRCORE4EOSC was intended to align closely with operational EOSC infrastructure, but the reconceptualisation of EOSC has complicated achieving project aims regarding the integration of the new FAIRCORE4EOSC components with the EOSC-Core. Due to the EOSC Federation and Node concept, introduced via the EOSC Procurement, the concepts of the Minimum Viable EOSC (MVE), the EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange and Federated Data as described in the “Solutions for a sustainable EOSC” -report from the Sustainability Working Group (2020) and used in the FAIRCORE4EOSC proposal and the project contract with the European Commission, became unclear and are still subject to change. The proposal and the Description of Action part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC Grant Agreement acknowledged that FAIRCORE4EOSC relies on the results of EOSC Future and could potentially be affected in an unfavourable way by the decisions taken by the EOSC Partnership and other actors.

Even though the context for the services has changed, the primary FAIRCORE4EOSC outputs to support a FAIR EOSC have just been released to the public (March 2025). Though many EOSC integrations have been tested, the current EOSC architecture does not support implementing integrations of the FAIRCORE4EOSC services as originally envisioned. All the services contribute to improving the discoverability and interoperability of a continuously increasing amount of research outputs, even with a looser EOSC coupling. They are discipline or geography agnostic and general in nature - and will surely gain further adoption both within and beyond EOSC. The plans for further service adoption are due to be released in May 2025 in the upcoming Deliverable 7.3 “Final Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities” (upcoming, 2025). The strategic alignment between the project and its various stakeholders is documented in “Deliverable 1.5 Strategic Alignment and Contribution to the EOSC Partnership” (Halonen et al., 2025).

¹Funding page in cordis: <https://doi.org/10.3030/101057264>

The work documented in this deliverable is based on the “Deliverable 1.2 FAIRCORE4EOSC Technical Specifications” (Suominen, Atzori, et al., 2023) and the management of the data sets is described in the Data Management Plan². This deliverable is structured according to the five tasks of this work package 4 (WP4). Each task starts with the original definitions of the task content. The first one (T4.1) is related to requirement collection and development of the architecture related to service integration using input from the use cases described by the (WP7) case studies. T4.2-4.4 document the details of service development for the three services in this work package (WP). T4.5 goes through the various demonstrators that have been implemented to validate the services. Finally, a cross-cutting activity is addressed: the planned integration to the EOSC-Core and the activities that consequently substituted it.

2 Task 4.1 Requirements, specifications and integration

Task definition: Task 4.1 Requirements, Specifications and Integration

Lead: SURF

Participants: CSC, INRIA, CLARIN, DATACITE, GRNET, DKRZ, HY

- **Develop requirements and specifications for the 3 registries and the (meta-)data interoperability service in collaboration with WP7 and relevant external stakeholders, building on the review of communities done for the SEMAF document**
- **Develop an architecture and data model for Metadata Schemas and Data Types**
- **Analysis and design of the integration with EOSC-Core services; EOSC-Exchange, EOSC marketplace, EOSC AAI, accounting, monitoring, usage statistics.**
- **Develop EOSC research activity workflow, beginning with EOSC service request and subsequent registration of EOSC RAiD, through research project completion**
- **Identify priority PIDs for the EOSC research activity workflow and define associated PID system information requirements**

2.1 Introduction and goals

The main goal of T4.1 was to set up a process for curating requirements from a variety of sources and for translating these requirements into technical specifications. Furthermore, the task focused on developing an architecture for the MSCR and DTR, designing integrations of the WP4 services, and establishing the EOSC research activity workflow. The task list above from the proposal describes these objectives, which are explained in more detail in the following sections.

2.2 Requirements and specifications: Collaborative definition, analysis, and development planning

Requirements and specifications were defined for each of the new core components using as a collaborative platform. Over time, the Jira platform was integrated with the project wiki (Confluence) to plan and track the component developments.

2.2.1 A customized Jira implementation for the consortium

Figure 1 provides a high-level overview of the process whereby case study teams defined requirements in the Jira. These teams analysed the requirements in collaboration with the component development teams to define the technical specifications, which were then used to develop the core components. Requirements and specifications were also collected during several community and EOSC events where the component

² <https://argos.openaire.eu/explore-plans/overview/public/dd4c79ed-1b43-41ad-81fa-f79da5af72eb>

development teams shared their development plans. In this case, the design ideas were added to the Jira by the development teams.

Figure 1 - Requirements process

Jira was configured at the beginning of the project in consultation with the Technical Steering Group and the Project Management Board. The custom configuration designed for the project is shown **Table 1. Jira configuration**, showing the fields and the instructions for using each field.

Table 1: Jira Configuration

Field	Instructions for content
Issue type	User "story"
Summary	Enter requirement number containing WP + task information + component name + short title Ex: "WP4.T4.4_RAiD Landing page in User Portal"
Reporter	Name of the creator of the ticket (your own)
Component/s	Select component(s), and case study if relevant. This is a predetermined list.
Description	Add here a description of the requirement. If it is a "user story" or "user requirement", add requirement context below as well. Advice: Copy-paste the below sections and fill them out: Where did a user find the problem / expect solutions to be found? Link, picture, place in the Portal etc Known constraints and considerations (provided by the user) Rules and limitations (e.g., time, resource, funding) that may dictate how the requirement is carried out User group(s) benefited: Researchers, Service/Resource Providers, Research communities, Research projects, Private company, Founder Authors Affiliation Who proposed the requirement? Organization Name
Business value	Use content from "User importance factor": 1 = Crucial; 2 = Important; 3 = Not Important
Linked Issues	Link to another Jira requirement if necessary (to note dependency)

Environment	Describe here the system environment, OS, relevant software
Source	Use content from “Channel” (E-mail, online survey, interview, JIRA etc.)
Priority	Set priority of requirement. Requirements by default are Major since they are expected to be mandatory. (Translation of H M L: H = Major; M = Minor; L = Trivial)
Labels	Add here relevant technologies, formats
Attachment	Add here relevant resources, files, screenshots
Assignee	Who will implement the requirement (Can leave empty for now)
Problem to be solved / user need	Describe the following context: What problem is the user trying to solve? What does the user need and want? What will the user achieve when the requirement is met?
Related use cases, real-life user scenarios	Describe the following context; Example: I'm a climate scientist. I'm looking for a specific set of data from Africa about the temp distribution in Kenia.
Contact point	Who should be contacted to provide the details/ verify the results?
Fix Version/s	Explanation: Used for periodic planning of the requirements

2.2.2 Instructions for requirements gathering in Jira

To ensure adoption of a custom Jira process, a set of materials were prepared for the consortium partners and delivered in various consortium-wide meetings:

- Instructions for requirements gathering
- Jira instructions: How to fill out tickets for requirements
- Product ownership cycle: Case study/demonstrator requirements
- Planning releases in Jira

Together, these materials instructed case study and component teams how to define, analyse and plan requirements collaboratively.

2.2.3 600+ requirements and specifications defined

Defining, analysing and implementing requirements occurred throughout the timeline of the project in order to capture interesting requirements which were outside of the scope of the project but potentially valuable to implement in the long-term. In total, 639 requirements and specifications were defined during the project (205 for the RAiD, 49 for the DTR and 86 for the MSCR). As requirements entered the Jira process, they were processed across teams using a customised Kanban workflow (shown in **Figure 2. Kanban workflow**). Teams added new requirements in consultation with project partners, and structured and refined them for implementation. Requirements were accepted and implemented or identified as out of scope.

Figure 2: Kanban workflow

Figure 3. Number of requirements shows the development of this definition over time in the project, whereby during Q1 of 2023 the largest upload of requirements in Jira took place after the requirements had been curated during the first 6 months of the project. The analysis of these requirements was staggered, initialised shortly after the Q1 2023 period, and expedited during Q4 2023. The acceptance of these requirements and their transition into development implementation followed the same pattern, while new requirements continued to be added throughout the project.

Figure 3: Number of requirements

Table 2. below provides an overview of requirements and specifications that were defined across the project, segmented by each case study, core component and the demonstrators.

Table 2: Overview of number of requirements

Case Study Requirements:	
CLIMATE CHANGE	46
MATHEMATICS	16
EUROPEAN INTEGRATION OF NATIONAL LEVEL SERVICES	24
SERVICE PROVIDERS AND RDM COMMUNITIES	10
SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES	19
Core Component Requirements and Specifications:	
CAT	84
DTR	49
MSCR	86
PIDGraph	48
PIDMR	72
RAiD	205
RDGraph	61
RSAC	60
Demonstrator Requirements:	
DEMONSTRATOR	70
Total Unique Requirements and Specifications	639

2.2.4 Supportive tooling for planning and tracking development

By leveraging the content curated in Jira, tools were created for the consortium to plan and track the component development and to support collaboration in this effort.

Software releases were configured in the project to enable the teams to build the components in development chunks. These releases were mostly mapped to development milestones and smaller development phases:

- M18: Beta release
- M22: Cross-integration and Case Studies Beta Integration Release
- M26: Final Integration 1/5
- M28: Final Integration 2/5
- M30: Final Integration 3/5
- M32: Final Integration 4/5
- M34: Production Release — Integration 5/5

Self-updating reports were generated in Confluence by connecting the platform to the Jira content. The reports were provided to the PMB for tracking the development of the components. The reports included:

- Requirements and their release plans

- ❑ Requirements, their analyses and acceptance/rejected for development
- ❑ Release plans and their progress
- ❑ Cross-analysis of requirements which involve multiple components and/or case studies

The reports contained live content from Jira — being updated as Jira was updated; therefore, consortium members could interact with the reports by clicking the various links in the reports which would redirect them to the relevant requirements in Jira. For example, case study teams could click the links in the reports related to a single case study and be taken to a list of requirements in Jira to discuss with other consortium members. In this way the reports facilitated project collaboration.

2.3 Architecture and data model

While the dedicated teams carried out the development work of the MSCR and DTR components, here, an architectural view of these two components has been brought together in alignment with EOSC standards and the designs of the EOSC-Core architecture at the time. During the project, the EOSC architecture was made obsolete by the federated design of EOSC nodes (see the EOSC Federation Handbook, (EOSC Association, 2025)).

Figure 4: MSCR Architectural Overview (1)

Figure 5: MSCR Architectural Overview (2)

Figure 6: DTR Architectural overview

In **Figure. 4** and **5**, the first two levels of the C4 diagram for the MSCR are shown, and in **Figure. 6**, the same levels for the DTR are shown (in this case, in a single diagram). In the DTR diagram, “external DTRs” are additional DTR instances that can be integrated to achieve a federated service. The levels of the architectural diagram shown are enough to understand the role of these services in the broader EOSC structure, indicated in the diagram as different EOSC Core components. These teams worked on the integration and implementation of the EOSC services in the EOSC platform during multiple co-creation events, often following up on key deliverables of the project – for example, after Deliverable 1.3, which outlined the initial integration plans

Integration analysis and design

The project was also designed to support the integration of the new core components with the existing EOSC services and with the other new core components. These integrations were mostly designed in collaboration with the FAIRCORE4EOSC consortium teams and the EOSC Future teams.

- Technical Project Meeting 1, April 2023 (Kajaani)
- EOSC Winter School Internal Project Meeting, January 2024 (Thessaloniki)
- Technical Project Meeting 2, April 2024 (Athens)
- Technical Project Meeting 3, October 2024 (Berlin)
- EUDAT Workshop, December 20254 (Karlsruhe)

The designs of the EOSC integration for each component are based on the guidelines from the EOSC Future and EOSC Beyond projects. Below, **Figure 7. Core component cross-integration design** illustrates the designs for cross-integration between the core components. This design was first drafted and then refined during the technical project meetings between the component development teams, case study teams and the Technical Steering Group.

Figure 7: Core component cross-integration design

2.4 EOSC research activity workflow

The EOSC RAiD service is delivered to EOSC users via an integration with the EOSC Marketplace project. EOSC users can log in to the EOSC platform via the AAI and go to the Marketplace to create RAiDs for their projects, as shown for the entity “EOSC user” in **Figure 8. EOSC research activity marketplace integration** below. The coloured lines and entities indicate which components of this integration are involved in delivering this service to EOSC users.

Users can mint (create) RAiDs via a GUI presented to them in the EOSC Marketplace, and request access to the EOSC RAiD service hosted at SURF. The GUI offers a form for users to fill out core metadata required for a RAiD, supported by the RAiD API, and connections to ORCID and ROR. When users mint new RAiDs using this API connection to SURF’s RAiD instance, these RAiDs are registered in the dedicated EOSC RAiD repositories in DataCite. Users can then continue to manage these RAiDs either via the marketplace or directly through SURF.

Figure 8: EOSC Research Activity Marketplace Integration

2.5 Priority PIDS for the EOSC research activity workflow

A total of 31 requirements were defined for the RAiD service and its interaction with other PID systems. The most important PIDs for RAiD offered via the EOSC Marketplace project are ORCID and ROR.

- RAiD is bidirectionally integrated with ORCID, so that when users add ORCIDs as RAiD contributors, users are guided via a workflow to verify this connection between the RAiD record and their ORCID. In the end, the RAiD contains the ORCID and the ORCID profile contains the RAiD.
- In respect of ROR integration, should users start typing their organisation name in the EOSC Marketplace, a list of matching organisation names from ROR is offered for selection to enter into the RAiD record. Entering a ROR manually is also possible.

2.6 Learning and applying experience, during the project and after

Naturally, throughout the FAIRCORE4EOSC project many lessons were learnt along the way which can be addressed in follow-up projects. Action was also taken directly during the project to respond to lessons learnt as the project progressed. An example is discussed below.

After about a year of working with the project’s Jira requirements, it was found that interaction with Jira was mostly occurring for designing, analysing, and collaborating within the small teams that were formed, either formally in the project — for example, around the case studies and their relevant components — or informally, in the case of teams that worked closely together around specific topics. To refine the planning and implementation activities of the component development, T4.1 created a series of live reports in Confluence which enabled any members of the consortium (in addition to the Technical Steering Group) to

analyse the status of requirements at a high level at any point in the project. Furthermore, these Confluence reports provided cross-analysis of requirements which involved (multiple) components and case studies. As such, these reports provided a basis for WP7 to plan targeted collaboration around specific topics between teams across the work-packages. Alongside Jira, Confluence reports provided a set of design, planning and implementation tools for the project, across WP's, the PMB and TSG.

Not all steps to refine the processes were effective, however. During the Technical Meeting 2, it was found that teams were struggling to implement large chunks of work aligned to milestones or deliverable points in the project. To aid this, T4.1 configured periodic releases in the project Jira and instructed the component teams how to plan their requirements for specific releases, with the aim of implementing small batches of requirements gradually over time. While the planned releases were used by some, it was not a planning method easily implemented across the project teams. While value was seen, feedback was received from some teams that the requirements process was too cumbersome at times. The balance between thoroughness and practicality of these project management methods was difficult to achieve. Nevertheless, many teams — especially WP7 — were satisfied with the requirements process.

During the project, some requirements which were suggested were seen as out-of-scope. In total, 71 requirements were rejected, and a subset of these (37 at the time of writing this deliverable), were proposed for development in a project. future projects.

3 Task 4.2 EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registries

Task definition: Task 4.2 EOSC Metadata Schema and Cross-walk Registries

Lead: CSC

Participants: SURF, CLARIN, GRNET, AGH/AGH-UST

- Develop and establish the EOSC MSCR with capacity to harvest schemas/crosswalks hosted elsewhere as well as hosting them in the repository**
- Develop the mechanism and guidelines for community or individual users to register metadata schemas and create a GUI for visually creating crosswalks (such as the output of the Ariadne project)**
- Develop an API and guidelines for organisations to register and maintain metadata schemas and crosswalks in the EOSC MSCR**
- Integrate MSCR with the EOSC-Core services**
- Align the metadata schema and crosswalk registration process and governance with the EOSC Provider and Resource onboarding process (currently operated by EOSC Future)**
- Create a (meta-)data interoperability service that facilitates conversion between metadata schemas**
- Integrate Data Type Registry in the metadata schema registry's (meta-)data interoperability service, using the Data Type Registry API**

Key service Info for the EOSC Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR)

- Production Release: Yes, 30-05-2025**
- Stable Software Release: Yes, 31-03-2025**
- Agreement documents: No, planned 31-05-2025**
 - o **Privacy Statement (DPS):** <https://mscr-release.2.rahtiapp.fi/privacy-guideline>
 - o **Service Level Specifications (SLS):** n/a
 - o **Terms of Use (ToU):** <https://cscfi.github.io/mscr-docs/terms-of-use/>
 - o **Acceptable Use Policy (AUP):** <https://cscfi.github.io/mscr-docs/acceptable-use-policy/>
- User Documentation:** <https://cscfi.github.io/mscr-docs/>
- Interoperability Guidelines: Planned 31-05-2025**
- Code properly Published/Archived:** <https://github.com/orgs/CSCfi/teams/mscr/repositories>
- Integration with EOSC Innovation Sandbox: EOSC Beyond Sandbox AAI**

3.1 Introduction to MSCR development

The Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR) development project set out to implement a solution that would fulfil the three main requirements: provide a registry for existing schemas and crosswalks, create a tool for defining and describing crosswalks between existing schemas, and facilitate the transformation of (meta)data documents using crosswalks created with the MSCR. The implemented MSCR service contributes to the FAIRness of research related data by making its metadata (schemas) more findable and accessible, it promotes discoverability, accessibility and re-usability of crosswalks through uniquely identified, uniform and structured mapping sets, and allows crosswalk specifications to be made directly interoperable through artefacts generated for crosswalk operationalisation.

The features and especially their implementation details were designed based on the requirements gathered from the demonstrators and case studies involved in the project. In addition, the goal of providing concrete support for actual data transformation (i.e. operationalisation of the crosswalk) had a considerable influence on the implementation details of all the other features. If one works backwards from the data transformation via MSCR crosswalks:

- There is a need for the crosswalks to be defined in a way that allows for precise identification of all the possible elements of both source and target schemas.
- From the case studies, it was determined that there was a variety of schemas that could act as a source or a target of a crosswalk. Some cases dealt with vocabularies, some with data schemas.
- It would not be enough to support simple one-to-one mappings, but some of the crosswalk use cases in the project called for complex structural and value changes.
- To support the operationalisation of these complex mappings between diverse types of schemas, the mappings would need to be described and stored in an actionable format.
- No common standard way of representing all those cases existed at the time, hence a custom format was needed.
- Finally, going from crosswalk definition to schema registration, it would not be enough to register metadata about the schemas because the actual content was also needed to support the crosswalk editor.
 - o It is straight-forward to store the schema files along with the metadata, but in order to make them mappable with the crosswalk editor the schemas would also needed to be parsed and processed, which is challenging given the variety of schema description formats coming from the case studies and demonstrators.
 - o This meant that MSCR could not be "just" a registry of metadata about schemas and crosswalks (like for example RDA Metadata Standards Catalog - <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>), nor would it be enough to act as repository for schema files (e.g. Github repositories).
 - o The requirement for facilitating data transformation meant that the internal data model of the MSCR had to cater for both the meta models of the supported schema description languages and complex mappings between them.

3.1.1 Technical foundations

In order to get a head start on the implementation of the MSCR, a set of mapping related tools and services were first evaluated for their suitability as the technological foundation. The main problem with the existing solutions was that they were usually focused on just one type of mappings. For example, Cocoda (<https://coli-conc.gbv.de/cocoda/>) is specifically designed for creating vocabulary to vocabulary mappings. More complex solutions such as like Data Modeling Environment (DME - <https://de.dariah.eu/en/dme>) that could handle the complexities of mapping requirements but had issues with sustainability or access to the source code. In the end, two solutions were selected for an in-depth technology review: Ontoport

(<https://ontportal.org/>) and Finnish Interoperability Platform (<https://dvv.fi/en/interoperability-platform>). The solutions were evaluated based on their technology choices, architecture, features, and sustainability. Both solutions were considered as highly suitable candidates, and had existing production deployments. Selection was ultimately determined by the existing skills and experience of the MSCR development team and the estimated time needed to adopt new technologies. The Finnish Interoperability Platform, with its familiar technology stack and solid sustainability plan, was selected as the basis for the MSCR implementation. Details of the technology review can be found in a separate MSCR Technology Review document. In a way, MSCR can be considered as a fourth component of the Finnish Interoperability Platform, which bridges the gap between data modelling and integration.

The MSCR code base was initialised by creating a fork from the [VRK-YTI Github repositories](#) maintained by the Digital and Population Data Services Agency (DVV) of Finland. At the start the MSCR development, DVV was in the process of implementing significant changes to the UI layer of the suite of services. The MSCR UI development was able to base its work on these new frameworks and components. Given that the extensive DVV update process was still in its early days, the starting point for the backend was the current (or "old") production branch, for which the development team had previous experience and the development could start with a minimal learning curve. In respect of future development of the MSCR code base, it would make sense to attempt to merge the latest updates from the DVV back-end with the MSCR code.

3.1.2 Components

Figure 9: MSCR component overview

MSCR components (see figure 9. for an overview):

- UI:** Nextjs application.
- Authentication proxy:** Acts as a Shibboleth proxy for authenticated uses.
- Datamodel-api:** Datamodel-api is the main backend component of the MSCR.
- Messaging-api:** Manages user subscriptions to content notifications and queries datamodel-api for changes to the subscribed content.
- Group management:** Group management component includes UI and API for managing groups, users and their roles. Users also use group management service to retrieve their API tokens. Datamodel-api synchronizes its internal cache of users and groups from the group management service.
- Triplestore:** RDF database is the main source of all the processed and mappable schema content as well as crosswalk created with the crosswalk editor.
- Search index:** All search requests are made against the search index. Datamodel-api is responsible for keeping the index up to date.
- Relational database:** Relational database is used by the group management service to maintain group and user information. Datamodel-api service uses database to store schema and crosswalk files and their metadata.
- XSLT transformer:** This service provides a simple API for executing XSLT transformations. Implementation is based on SAXON (community edition) and supports XSLT 3.0. The service should only be exposed to datamodel-api service. The main purpose of this service to provide testing facilities for crosswalk editor. See "Transformation" section below for more information.
- RML transformer:** This service transforms CSV/XML/JSON document to RDF using RMLmapper (<https://github.com/RMLio/RML-Mapper>) library. The service should only be exposed to datamodel-api service. The main purpose of this service to provide testing facilities for crosswalk editor. See "Transformation" section below for more information.

3.1.3 Metadata model

This section describes the metadata model for the data that is intended for external clients such as harvesters or custom mapping UI tools. The metadata model is used when creating or updating content through the API and when fetching metadata about content with a given internal ID or a PID. Summary of general metadata fields and additional crosswalk metadata fields can be found in tables 3. ja 4. respectively.

Schema

Table 3: General MSCR public metadata model fields

Field	Datatype	Description	is multivalued
type	string	The nature or genre of the resource. (dct:type - DCTERMS). Values: SCHEMA, CROSSWALK	
status	string	The status of the resource in the context of a particular workflow process (adms:status - ADMS). Values: DRAFT, PUBLISHED, DEPRECATED, INVALID, REMOVED	
dateSubmitted	string	Date and time when the metadata record was created. Date of submission of the resource (dct:dateSubmitted - DCTERMS)	

Field	Datatype	Description	is multivalued
modified	string	Date and time when metadata record was last changed (dct:modified - DCTERMS)	
contactPoint	string	Relevant contact information for the cataloged resource (dcat:contactPoint - DCAT3).	
creator	string	An entity primarily responsible for making the resource (dct:creator) (DCTERMS).	x
identifier	string	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context. This includes the MSCR minted handle prefix if the content has been published (dct:identifier -DCTERMS).	x
issued	string	Date of formal issuance of the resource (dct:issued - DCTERMS).	
language	string	A language of the resource (dct:language - DCTERMS).	
license	string	A legal document giving official permission to do something with the resource (dct:license - DCTERMS).	
publisher	string	An entity responsible for making the resource available (dct:publisher - DCTERMS).	
description	string	An account of the resource (dct:description - DCTERMS).	
title	string	A name given to the resource (dct:title - DCTERMS).	
format	string	CSV, XSD, JSONSchema, RDFS, SHACL, OWL, SKOS, PDF, ENUM, MSCR (dct:format - DCTERMS).	
contributor	string	An entity responsible for making contributions to the resource (dct:contributor - DCTERMS).	x
source	string	URL used to register the content. A related resource from which the described resource is derived (dct:source - DCTERMS).	
downloadUrl	string	Link to the registered file. The URL of the downloadable file in a given format. E.g., CSV file or RDF file (dcat:downloadURL - DCAT 3).	
keyword	string	A keyword or tag describing the resource (dcat:keyword - DCAT3)	
landingPage	string	Link to the MSCR UI page of the content. A Web page that can be navigated to in a Web browser to gain access to the catalog, a dataset, its distributions and/or additional information (dcat:landingPage - DCAT3).	
previousVersion	string	ID of the previous content version. The previous version of a resource in a lineage (dcat:previousVersion - DCAT3).	
visibility	string	Whether or not the content is searchable. Values: PUBLIC, PRIVATE (mscr:visibility).	
domain	string	Text field to describe domain related to the content (mscr:domain).	
internalID	string	MSCR ID of the content (mscr:id).	
handle	string	Handle identifier for the metadata record (mscr:handle).	

Crosswalk

Crosswalks share the metadata model with schemas with the following additional fields.

Table 4: MSCR Crosswalk's addition metadata fields

Field	Datatype	Description	Example value
sourceSchema	string	Handle or internal ID of the source schema.	mscr:schema:8bbe05f5-31c3-46e7-8e74-1220f5bb3c45
targetSchema	string	Handle or internal ID of the target schema.	21.T13999/EOSC-202502000405042
format	string	PDF, CSV, XSLT, SSSOM, MSCR	

Mapping

Metadata model of a single mapping is a subset of the fields (Table 5.) defined in the SSSOM (Matentzoglou et al., 2022) specification³. Mapping metadata can be used to further describe the context in which an individual mapping has been created to evaluate the applicability of the crosswalk to the task at hand.

MSCR mapping has the following metadata fields (descriptions are adapted from the SSSOM specification).

Table 5: MSCR mapping metadata fields

Field	Description
mapping_date	The date the mapping was asserted.
confidence	A score between 0 and 1 to denote the confidence or probability that the match is correct, where 1 denotes total confidence.
justification	A mapping justification is an action (or the written representation of that action) of showing a mapping to be right or reasonable.
comment	Free text field containing either curator notes or text generated by tool providing additional informative information.
reviewer_id	Identifies the persons or groups that reviewed and confirmed the mapping. Recommended to be a list of ORCIDs or otherwise identifying URIs.

3.1.4 Content lifecycle

All MSCR content (schemas/crosswalks) is associated with a state metadata field. Possible state values and transitions between them can be seen in Figure 10.

³ <https://mapping-commons.github.io/sssom/>

Figure 10: MSCR content states

MSCR states:

- DRAFT - Should only be used for incomplete content. Content in DRAFT state can disappear and change at any time without notice.
- PUBLISHED - Active and current version.
- DEPRECATED - Active but retired/replaced version.
- INVALID - Should not be used anymore.
- REMOVED - Content not available anymore.

MSCR content is only editable in DRAFT state and after that modifications can only be made to the metadata record. Established and retired schemas can be registered directly to PUBLISHED or DEPRECATED state respectively. Once the content is removed, it enters REMOVED state where the content is removed but metadata record remains and is presented to any user trying to access the content (tombstoning).

3.1.5 Content ownership

In MSRC the content ownership can be assigned to an individual user or group. This role provides the user or users in the owner group the permission to modify content and metadata. In the MSCR UI the ownership of a new content is determined based on the context (personal or group workspace) from which the user starts the registration/creation process.

It is possible to change the ownership of the content between personal account and a group account if the user who owns the content is also a member of the target group with EDITOR role. The same applies to moving content between groups i.e. the user must have EDITOR role in both source and target groups.

When the ownership is transferred the content is also moved from one workspace to another. It is currently not possible to move content owned by a group to an individual user.

3.1.6 Persistent identifiers

MSCR content is assigned a handle based persistent identifier (PID) when it is published. Publishing can happen either directly from the registration form or when the user changes the status of the content from DRAFT to PUBLISHED. Individual mappings in a crosswalk are identified by a part identifier that are based on the PID of the crosswalk. These identifiers are of the form <CROSSWALK_HANDLE>@mapping=<UUID>. MSCR PIDs resolve to special "resolve" endpoint that uses the ACCEPT header of the HTTP request to determine where to redirect the request (Table 6).

Table 6: PID redirection summary

ACCEPT value	Redirection target
text/html	Metadata and files tab of the content. (default) Example: /datamodel-api/v2/crosswalk/mscr:crosswalk:0adb14e2-f0d7-441a-ae26-11bdc8fb59cf/
application/json	JSON serialization of the content metadata or mappings. Example: /datamodel-api/v2/crosswalk/mscr:crosswalk:0adb14e2-f0d7-441a-ae26-11bdc8fb59cf

3.1.7 Integrations

AAI

MSCR inherited its SAML based authentication mechanism from the Finnish Interoperability Platform. During the project MSCR service was integrated with two different EOSC project related AAI infrastructures and finally with the B2ACCESS production AAI. Integrating with a well-connected federation ensures that users can easily access the MSCR regardless of their home organisation.

FAIRCORE4EOSC WP4 services

The services within the WP4 (MSCR, DTR, Vicabulary Service) are dealing with similar and related types of content, and as a result they provide opportunities for integration. For the MSCR there are two main use cases for vocabulary and DTR integration: schema editing and schema mapping. Although MSCR is not a schema editor, it does provide schema editing features that are related to creating crosswalks (See section "Content management" for more information).

The MSCR allows users to associate properties of a registered schema with basic data types defined in the DTR. This means that one can, for example, replace a generic "string" datatype in a JSONSchema specification, with a more expressive DTR data type, such as "handle", which can provide additional textual description of the values as well as a regular expression pattern for value validation. This is helpful for mapping especially if the person creating the crosswalk is not that familiar with the actual instance data being mapped. For example, a handle field might contain only the identifier or it could be used to store a full URL (2341/12345 vs. hdl.handle.net/2341/12345). Associating property with a DTR data type reference can make the format explicit and hence inform the user whether a function needs to be applied to remove or append the "hdl.handle.net" prefix.

In respect to the schema mapping use case, both DTR and the Vocabulary Service are capable of exporting content that can be used as the source for MSCR schema registration. The reason why one might like to register content from these systems can be for example data transformation or semantic mapping. The DTR type API (ref X) can export complex data types as JSON schemas. Although these schemas are more for data transformation purposes, they do contain JSON-LD elements, namely @id and @type, which make them also suitable for other mapping cases. For an example of data transformation via MSCR crosswalk, see the Climate Change case study (ref X). From the MSCR's perspective, vocabularies are "just" another type of schema and therefore content maintained in the Vocabulary Service can be registered with MSCR for semantic mapping purposes. Integration is made possible by the SKOS export feature of the Vocabulary Service. See Figure 11. for an overview of the WP4 service integrations.

Figure 11: Overview of the WP4 integration use cases.

3.1.8 FAIRness of MSCR

As the goal of the MSCR is to make schemas and crosswalks more FAIR, it is appropriate to evaluate the FAIRness of MSCR content. The FAIR Mappings recommendations (Le Franc et al., 2025), published by the FAIR-Impact project in April 2025, are used as the baseline against which to appraise the features of the MSCR. The document presents 18 recommendations (4 generic and 14 technical) grouped into four categories: Model and format, Metadata, PID and Service and API.

Model and format

MSCR does have a model that contains mappings, mapped entities and metadata and links between them as recommended (G-Rec 1). The model is MSCR specific but can be mapped to other models such a SSSOM (T-Rec 1.1). MSCR allows users to register their mappings using SSSOM (see X), edit them with crosswalk editor (See Y) and export new version of the mappings as SSSOM. Mappings to other formats can be added as needed and the future developments should keep watch for output from groups such as the RDA FAIR Mappings Working Group (WG). The MSCR mapping model can be downloaded in multiple serialisation formats (see section "Operationalisation support") (T-Rec 1.2) and the content metadata is an application profile that consists of properties from well known vocabularies such as Dublin Core (DCTERMS), DCAT (DCAT3) and ADMS (ADMS) (T-Rec 1.3).

Metadata

MSCR has metadata for both crosswalk and individual mappings (see section "Metadata model") as recommended (G-Rec 2). Crosswalk level metadata in MSCR is not solely based on the recommended SSSOM model (T Rec 2.1), but it contains many similar elements which makes it possible to generate the most important parts of the SSSOM header. For individual mappings, the MSCR metadata model is a subset of the SSSOM metadata model as recommended (T Rec 2.1).

Persistent identifiers

Persistent identifier related recommendations revolve around using Globally Unique, Persistent, Resolvable Identifiers (GUPRIs) for everything from crosswalks to individual mappings (G Rec 3). MSCR's usage of handles for crosswalks and schemas and handles with part identifiers (see "Persistent identifiers") adheres to this recommendation and the lifecycle model creates a solid foundation for service providers to implement their PID policies (T Rec 3.2).

Services and API

MSRC allows the preservation and presentation of all existing identifiers of existing schemas and crosswalks. New identifiers are minted for all content metadata records as well as mappings created with the crosswalk editor (T Rec 4.1). The API can be used to fetch metadata about content using both internal identifiers and handles (T Rec 4.2) and each version has its own handle and hence metadata record (T Rec 4.3). Editing rights to mappings are controlled using roles (T Rec 4.4) and if a published content is ever removed the metadata is still accessible through the API (See "Content lifecycle") (T Rec 4.5). Schemas and crosswalks are searchable (T Rec 4.6), but there is currently no way to directly search for individual mappings. Finally, MSCR API specification is available in the OpenAPI format and a Swagger UI is accessible as part of the service (T Rec 4.7).

In summary, the MSCR fulfils most of the FAIR recommendations outlined in the first version of the FAIR-Impact FAIR Mappings recommendations, but there is room for improvement especially with respect to features related to reusability of individual mappings.

3.2 MSCR Vocabulary Service

During the first round of requirement collection from demonstrators and case studies, requirements related to creating and maintaining vocabularies started to emerge. It became clear that it was not enough to be able to map vocabularies or controlled lists, but there was also a need for a service that could be used to manage vocabularies. This service was outside of the planned scope of the MSCR and would be required also be required by the MSCR for value mappings. The Compliance Assessment Toolkit (CAT), also expressed an interest in and need for a service to create and manage variety of vocabularies required to run the CAT service. A decision was made to add vocabulary service as the tenth component and to use the existing services from the Finnish Interoperability Platform as the starting point for the implementation.

The Finnish Interoperability Platform has separate services and UIs for managing terminologies and codelists, The Terminology Service is designed to support the management of specific kind of the controlled lists called terminologies, which is reflected to the kind of features the service provides. Similarly, the Codelist or Reference Data Service is purpose built to handle specific type of data. It was not feasible for the MSCR development team to set up two new services in addition to the MSCR, so a decision was made to customise the Terminology Service into a general vocabulary service. At the UI level, the customisations related mainly to the simplification of the views by removing unnecessary components. In the backend, the major changes were the related to switching from the URL based identifier system to handles and the

addition of SKOS based import and export functionality. Vocabularies exported as SKOS can be registered easily to the MSCR for mapping.

3.3 MSCR features/ requirements included in the final release

This section gives an overview of the main features of the MSCR release. See user documentation for the more details.

3.3.1 Content registration

Content registration allows adding existing content to the MSCR. Content must be provided in one of the supported file formats and it can be uploaded from the local machine as part of the registration process or referenced using an URL. All registered content consists of a metadata record and a bitstream that is used to store the original version of the content.

The user can set the state of the content as part of the registration process to DRAFT, PUBLISHED or DEPRECATED. DRAFT state should be used for content that might still require some changes or where metadata is not yet available, whereas content that is already in use can be registered directly as PUBLISHED. Registering content as DEPRECATED makes sense when there is a need to support mappings to and from older and superseded, but still actively used schemas.

Schemas

Table 7. summarises the schema description languages supported by the MSCR. CSV, XSD, JSON Schema, RDFS, SHACL, OWL, SKOS and ENUM are mappable formats that can be used when creating a new crosswalk with the crosswalk editor. Each schema format has its own peculiarities and versions and the MSCR can only handle some versions and specific subsets of features. This means for example that it is not possible to register every possible JSON Schema file as a mappable schema. In such cases, it is still possible to register any schema in a supported format with an option that skips the processing part (see user guide⁴ for details). This means that the metadata and schema file would still be managed by MSCR, but the schema would not be available to be used with the crosswalk editor.

Some schema description formats support modular schema, which consist of multiple files that are combined using different kinds of import mechanisms. Modular schemas are supported only for JSONSchema and XSD formats and they should only be used with URL based schema registrations, since content registration supports uploading of only one file.

PDF schemas are the only ones that cannot be used with the crosswalk editor. The PDF format is supported for legacy reasons to give users a way to register documentation related to the schema or schemas only available in unstructured form.

Table 7: Summary of MSCR supported schema file formats

Format	Media type	Mappable	Sub type	Notes
CSV	text/csv	yes	Data schema	File must contain only one line with fields separated by comma.
XSD	text/xml	yes	Data schema	Not all features of XSD are supported.

⁴ <https://cscfi.github.io/mscr-docs/>

Format	Media type	Mappable	Sub type	Notes
JSON Schema	application/json	yes	Data schema	Implementation based on draft-04. No support for allOf, oneOf, anyOf or not.
RDFS	text/turtle	yes	Data schema	Processed as data schema (see X) so visualization requires the use of rdfs:domain and rdfs:range properties.
SHACL	text/turtle	yes	Data schema	Only supported RDF format is turtle.
OWL	text/turtle	yes	Ontology	Only supported RDF format is turtle.
SKOS	text/turtle	yes	Vocabulary	Only supported RDF format is turtle.
ENUM	text/plain	yes	Vocabulary	One line per term.
PDF	application/pdf	no		

Once the schemas have been successfully registered, it is browsable using the MSCR schema view. The schema view is divided into three tabs:

- "Metadata and files" tab show all the metadata available for the content and lists download links to the original content as well as links to the generated internal representation for CSV, XSD and JSONSchema formats.
- "Schema" tab shows a visualisation of the schema using a tree structure. The content of the tree is dependent of the schema format. For CSV, XSD and JSON Schema the tree shows the fully materialised structure of the schema (see figure X) i.e. all the possible elements.
- "Versions" tab lists all the related versions for the given content and provided a user to navigate between them.

Crosswalks

MSCR supports four formats for registering existing crosswalks: PDF, CSV, XSLT and SSSOM (see Table 8). Only one of them, SSSOM, is editable and the others are only available for download. PDF has remained a popular format for describing crosswalks up to this date. For example, DataCite has published crosswalks to Dublin Core (DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2021) and schema.org (Stathis et al., 2022) in PDF format. The other popular way of describing correspondences is a table or a set of tables. For example, CodeMeta crosswalks⁵ are a good example of simple mappings expressed as CSV files. A generic table format without any additional information does not provide any information about the meaning of columns being used so it is not usable to for automated processing and is therefore not editable in MSCR. XML stylesheets (XSLT) are of also still a common tool when it comes to applying transformations between XML documents. It is a powerful tool with mapping possibility that go far beyond the mapping model of the MSCR. SSSOM on the other hand has a simple model with restricted and very focused feature set geared towards sharing of semantic mappings. MSCR can convert the registered SSSOM file into its internal mapping representation and therefore the SSSOM crosswalk can be edited and viewed similarly to any crosswalk created from scratch with the crosswalk editor.

⁵ <https://codemeta.github.io/crosswalk/>

Table 8: Summary of MSCR supported crosswalk file formats

Format	Media type	Editable	Sub type
SSSOM	text/csv	yes	Semantic mapping
Table	text/csv	no	
XSLT	text/xml	no	
PDF	application/pdf	no	

The MSCR crosswalk is always registered with information about both the source and target schema of the crosswalk. The default option is to refer to already registered schemas within the MSCR. This makes the connection between the crosswalk and the schemas explicit and provides a way of using the MSCR to access the schema content (for example for validation purposes). This is also a prerequisite for using the crosswalk editor to edit the crosswalk. However, it is not always convenient to require schemas to be first registered in the MSCR. For example, they may be in a unsupported format or they may already be maintained by another service and there is no motivation to create a separate MSCR instance of the schemas. In these cases, a crosswalk can be registered with implicit references to the source and target schemas. This kind of "detached" crosswalk still requires information about the source and target schemas, but the description can be any textual content e.g. a PID or a short description of the schema. MSCR does not provide any kind of visualisation or editing support for crosswalks that do not provide explicit references to MSCR schemas. It is also not possible to register a crosswalk with one explicit and one implicit schema reference.

3.3.2 Search and browse

MSCR provides basic search and browse functionality for all schemas and crosswalks that have their visibility set to PUBLIC. This means that all content that is not in DRAFT state is findable through the search. The API provides different endpoints for searching content in three different contexts: public, personal and group. The main difference between public and the two others is that personal and group searches require an API key and are therefore able to return content also in a DRAFT state with VISIBILITY set to PRIVATE. Search endpoints implement a basic faceted search with the possibility to have a free text query with a field (e.g. state, type, format, group..) based filters. The text query targets the dct:title and dct:identifier metadata fields. Other searchable fields are listed in table 9.

Figure 12: General public MSCR search UI

Search returns only the latest revision of the content by default. This means that if there are older revisions that have slightly different metadata (e.g. the name) they may not appear in the results. It is possible to extend the search to all revisions by adding the "includeRevisions" parameter. This can significantly increase the number of returned results, but can be helpful in specific situations especially when combined with the "versionLabel" facet filter.

Table 9: List of searchable fields.

Name	Description	is available as a facet
type	SCHEMA/CROSSWALK	x
state	DRAFT, PUBLISHED, DEPRECATED, INVALID, REMOVED	x
organisations	UUID of the owner organization	
format	PDF/CSV/XSLT/SSSOM/MSCR/XSD/JSONSCHEMA/RDFS/SHACL/OWL/SKOSRDF/ENUM	x
sourceSchemas	Internal ID or handle of the source schema (for crosswalk type only)	
targetSchemas	Internal ID or handle of the target schema (for crosswalk type only)	
subtype	DATA SCHEMA/VOCABULARY/ONTOLOGY/DATA_CROSSWALK/SEMANTIC_MAPPING/SEMANTIC_ANNOTATION	x
versionLabel	Version information.	x
publisher		
identifier	External identifiers	
description	Optional text describing the content	

3.3.3 Crosswalk editor

The crosswalk editor is an integrated tool that allows users to create and edit complex mappings between two registered MSCR schemas. The crosswalk editor supports creation of mappings between any of the following schema formats: CSV, XSD, JSON Schema, RDFS, SHACL, OWL, SKOS, and ENUM. The MSCR allows users to mix-and-match different formats freely and they are all called crosswalks in the UI. Internally, crosswalks are categorised into "crosswalk", "semantic mapping" or "semantic annotation" sub-types based on the format of the source and target schemas. The rules for determining the crosswalk sub type is summarised in table X. Sub-types describe the goal or purpose of the mapping:

- Data crosswalks: the purpose of the mappings is to transform an instance document that conforms to the source schema into another instance document that conforms to the target schema with potentially complex processing.
- Semantic mappings: describes a correspondence with possible ontological commitment between two identified entities, such as vocabulary concepts, classes or properties.

- Annotations: A set of mappings between "just strings" i.e. lexical tokens and identified semantic entities such as SKOS vocabulary concepts or OWL classes is categorised as semantic annotation.

Table 10: Source and target type to subtype mapping

Source schema format	Target schema format	Crosswalk sub type
CSV/XML/JSONSCHEMA/SHACL	CSV/XML/JSONSCHEMA/SHACL	DATA_CROSSWALK
CSV/XML/JSONSCHEMA	RDFS/OWL/SKOS	SEMANTIC_ANNOTATION
RDFS/OWL/SKOS/ENUM	RDFS/OWL/SKOS/ENUM	SEMANTIC_MAPPING

The UI uses crosswalk sub-type categorisation information to show and hide certain components that are not relevant to the given crosswalk type. For example, the mapping predicate is only relevant for individual mappings that are part of a semantic annotations or mappings crosswalk. For these cases the MSCR UI provides a fixed set of supported predicates derived from SKOS and OWL vocabularies such as `skos:exactMatch` and `owl:equivalentClass`. As an example, a triple `dct:title skos:exactMatch mscr:name`, indicates with a high degree of confidence that `dct:title` and `mscr:name` can be used interchangeably across different applications. If the source and target can always be used interchangeably in all current and future cases, a mapping `dct:title owl:sameAs mscr:name` could be used. However, this kind of mapping comes with a very different ontological commitment compared to the `skos:exactMatch` version. For data crosswalks the predicate field in the UI is replaced in by functions. Again, MSCR provides a fixed set of supported functions for the user to choose from. The exact list of available functions depends on the formats of source and target schemas due to the different operationalisation support implementations (see section "Operationalisation support").

The MSCR mapping model supports source, mapping and target functions. Source function can be used, for example, to harmonise values of a many-to-one mapping by removing whitespace and it always takes the value of a single property as an input. Input for the mapping function is always an array consisting of values of all the source properties that could have been modified by source functions. Finally, the target function takes as input the mapping function output, allowing for final modifications before the value is written to the target property (see Figure 13.).

Figure 13: Overview of MSCR mapping functions

This function model with a predefined set of operations and a maximum of three piped functions was designed to provide a compromise between flexibility and complexity.

3.3.4 Content management

Versioning

The MSCR versioning implementation distinguishes between variants and revisions. An MSCR revision is a version of a content that is closely related to a set of other versions. All related schema revisions share the same format and in the case of a crosswalk also the source and target schemas (See Figure 14.).

Figure 14: MSCR Revisions example

Versions				
Version label	PID	Created	State	
1	mscr:schema:7b2c7d6d-d989-4f07-af79-fdb88ef7809b	27/03/2025, 21.32	DRAFT	View
2	mscr:schema:6f9579d5-b904-44a1-b886-a38cdcbfcd7	30/03/2025, 20.21	DRAFT	Viewing

Content variants on the other hand are more loosely related. Variant schemas share the same namespace and crosswalks variants have the same source and target schemas, but the main difference to revisions is that the connections are created dynamically based on the metadata rather than by constraints set by the system. The purpose of the variants is to be able to see related content and potentially reuse it instead of creating identical copies, whereas revisions can be thought of as previous versions of the same content that are all grouped together. See Figure 15. for an illustration with example revisions and variants.

Figure 15: MSCR Versions and variants

Content copies

MSCR does not support direct copying of a schema. This restriction is in place to promote re-use of existing schemas and to curb the proliferation of identical content within MSCR. The only kind of copy that can be made is an MSCR copy. The MSCR copy is an editable version of a CSV, JSON Schema or XSD schema with the format set to "MSCR" and the initial state to DRAFT. The assumption is that the MSCR copy will be changed using the editing features of the MSCR, so that the content would not stay identical with source of

the copy action. Crosswalks are often highly contextual and for that reason it is possible to make a copy of any crosswalk that is editable and use it as a basis for a modified version of the crosswalk. MSCR keeps track of the source and target of a copy by adding `isCopyOf` and `hasCopy` triples to the graph whenever a copy of a content is created.

Schema editing

MSCR is not a schema editor per se but it does provide a limited set of the editing functionalities that are helpful for crosswalk editing. Schema editing is only available for schemas that are in MSCR format. It is possible to create a MSCR copy of a registered schema with some restrictions.

Adding DTR basic data types

The DTR integration (see section "Integrations!") allows basic data type information from the configured DTR instance to be searched and downloaded to the MSCR and incorporated into the MSCR schema. Adding a DTR type to a schema changes the data type of the property to the PID of the DTR data type and creates a copy of the type description in the MSCR for future reference.

Adding vocabulary restrictions to property values

It is possible to add value restrictions to schema properties that use primitive data types (e.g. string) using vocabularies registered with the MSCR. Referencing is done using the handle identifier, which means that the vocabulary must be published. This restriction also ensures that the values will not change unexpectedly.

Setting the root element

There are two basic use cases for setting a custom root element for a schema. In the first case the schema is modelled using multiple root level elements, but it is intended to be used for data mapping with a single root element. Setting a custom element in MSCR clears up the schema view for the schema by filtering out all unnecessary root elements. The other case for a custom root element is the filtering of large vocabularies or data schemas. For example, limiting the schema view to a specific branch of a vocabulary concepts for easier mapping.

3.3.5 User and group management

MSCR user and group management is handled by a separate group management application. This application has been re-used from the VRK-YTI repository with only minor modifications to the UI to hide some original branding and unnecessary links. Any logged in user can use the group management application to fetch their personal API access token. The access token can then be used to access the restricted API endpoints for creating and modifying content. Access tokens are valid for six months and they are always linked to a user. There is currently no method for creating real machine-to-machine type of tokens. If the token is lost or compromised the user can use the same UI to delete and regenerate it.

A new MSCR account is created for each user authenticate login through the integrated AAI. By default, all logged in users can register and create content in their personal workspace without restrictions. This of course opens the possibility of misuse, such as flooding the service with questionable content. If a more restrictive access policy is required, it is possible to configure the backend to require users to be part of at least one group before they can create new content.

The group management application provides a way for the MSCR administrators or superusers to manage a hierarchy of groups. Since groups can only be created by the service level administrator they can be used as an authoritative source for schemas and crosswalks. However, this requires that the processes for applying

and approving a new group must be handled outside of the MSCR. Given such approval process, it is then possible to manage the set of MSCR groups according to an agreed policy.

Superusers can add and remove users from any group. Users in a group can be associated with MEMBER or EDITOR roles. The EDITOR role can create and modify content in the group, whereas the only added capability for a MEMBER is to be able to access also the private content of the group. It is also possible to assign "group admin" role to one or more users in the group, which gives those users also the ability to add and remove users from the group. However, this feature in its current form is problematic from a user privacy perspective, since group admins, just like superusers, can search through the whole user base and see their names and email addresses.

3.3.6 Operationalisation support

The MSCR provides different kinds of generated artefacts for data transformation and semantic alignment scenarios. Data transformations are described as data crosswalk between data schemas (see section X) and are facilitated through generated files (e.g. XSLT) that can be executed by an external system to transform schema instance documents. The semantic alignment of vocabularies and ontologies is based on exporting mappings as SKOS and SSSOM files. Generated artefacts are available for download in the UI and through the API. See table 11. for a summary of artefacts per schema source and target format.

Data crosswalks

XSLT

Crosswalks can be exported as generated XSLT when the source and target schema format is one of CSV, XSD or JSON Schema. The generated XSLT file is completely self-contained and can be used as is for data transformation as is. All functions used in the crosswalk are mapped to native XSLT functions and the MSCR vocabulary-based value mappings are also embedded in the the generated file.

XML to XML transformations can be run with an XSLT 2.0 compliant processor but transformations involving CSV and JSON data requires support for version 3.0. CSV and JSON input must also be wrapped in <data> element and XML notation related characters (e.g. <, > and &) must be replaced with proper entities (e.g. <, > and &). Data preparation details are described in the user manual.

RML

RDF Mapping Language⁶ is a specification for defining transformation of CSV, XML and JSON documents to RDF. RML download is available for a MSCR crosswalk when the source schema format is one of CSV, XSD or JSONSchema and the target format is SHACL. RML based transformations are executed using an RML engine. MSCR generated RML mappings are tested with RMLMapper⁷, which has the required support for functions.

Transforming data with RMLMapper requires three inputs: source data, generated mapping file from the MSCR and a jar file containing the MSCR specific functions (available from MSCR GitHub repository). See the MSCR user guide for examples on how to run the RML mappings as well details related to the limitations of the current implementation.

⁶ <https://rml.io/>

⁷ <https://github.com/RMLio/RML-Mapper>

SPARQL - experimental

An experimental SPARQL construct select output is available for crosswalks between SHACL and CSV formats.

Semantic mappings

Semantic mappings between two vocabularies or ontologies can be exported in SKOS or SSSOM formats.

SKOS

The SKOS export renders the mappings that include predicate from the SKOS namespace⁸ as Turtle RDF triples. If the exported crosswalk contains mappings with predicates from other namespaces they are ignored and not included in the generated RDF.

For example, given the two simple vocabularies and their mappings:

```

voc1:concept1
  a skos:Concept ;
  skos:prefTitle "A" .

voc1:concept2
  a skos:Concept ;
  skos:prefTitle "B" .
    
```

Code block 1 Vocabulary 1

```

voc2:concept1
  a skos:Concept ;
  skos:prefTitle "1" .

voc2:concept2
  a skos:Concept ;
  skos:prefTitle "2" .
    
```

Code block 2 Vocabulary 2

Assuming the vo1:concept1 has exact match voc2:concept1 and voc1:concept2 with voc2:concept2 the crosswalk would produce the following SKOS export triples:

⁸ <http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#>

```

voc1:concept1 skos:exactMatch voc2:concept1 .
voc1:concept2 skos:exactMatch voc2:concept2

```

Code block 3 Mapping

The API allows one to include source and/or target schemas to the SKOS export (see MSCR API reference for details).

Example SKOS export with source schema included.

```

voc1:concept1
  a skos:Concept ;
  skos:prefTitle "A" ;
  skos:exactMatch voc2:concept1 .

voc1:concept2
  a skos:Concept ;
  skos:prefTitle "B" ;
  skos:exactMatch voc2:concept2 .

```

Code block 4 Mapping

SSSOM

A basic SSSOM file that includes all the fields available in the MSCR mapping model (see section "Metadata model") can be generated for crosswalks between ENUM, SKOS and OWL formatted schemas. Literal values from ENUM schemas are exported with the RDFS literal type as defined in the SSSOM specification. Basic mapping set metadata is included as a SSSOM header (See example below). For individual mappings, the notes field is mapped to SSSOM comment and mapping justification is automatically set to `semapv:ManualMappingCuration` since MSCR mappings are assumed to be created and curated manually. This is also the case with crosswalks that were imported as SSSOM, because the original mapping justification is not preserved.

```
#curie_map:
# skos: http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#
#mapping_set_id: https://hdl.handle.net/1234/1234566
#mapping_set_description: Description from MSCR
#mapping_tool: MSCR

#license: https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
#mapping_date: 2024-03-30
subject_id subject_label predicate_id object_id object_label
mapping_justification confidence comment reviewer_id
voc1:concept1 Test1 skos:exactMatch voc2:concept1 Test semapv:ManualMappingCuration
0.95 "Comment" "ORCID1"
voc1:concept2 Testing2 skos:exactMatch voc2:concept2 Test2
semapv:ManualMappingCuration 0.8 "Comment2" "ORCID2"
```

Example SSSOM export.

Table 11: Summary of operationalisation support

Source schema format	Target schema format	Generated output
CSV/XSD/JSONSchema	CSV/XSD/JSONSchema	XSLT
CSV/XSD/JSONSchema	SHACL	RML
SHACL	CSV	SPARQL
SKOS	SKOS	SKOS
ENUM/SKOS/OWL	ENUM/SKOS/OWL	SSSOM

3.3.7 Transformation

In addition to supporting the operationalisation of crosswalks through generated artefacts for data transformation, the MSCR also offers its own transformation features. These are simple services with the main purpose of helping with the testing of crosswalks built with the crosswalk editor. For this reason, the transformation services are currently available only for users who have editing rights to the crosswalk and only through a special "test" endpoint.

The test endpoint at "/v2/crosswalk/<CROSSWALK_ID>/test" is available for crosswalks where the source schema format is one of CSV, XSD or JSONSchema and the target schema format is one of CSV, XSD, JSONSchema or SHACL. The endpoint first generates a source schema document instance based on the source schema and an XSLT or RML file and then runs the transformation and finally returns the resulting document.

3.3.8 Notifications

Notifications are meant to make it easier for the users of the MSCR to co-develop schemas and crosswalks without the need to have direct communication about every change.

MSCR notifications are designed to allow users to subscribe to receive alerts if schema or crosswalk of their interest changes in a meaningful way. Notifications are delivered in a form for a digest email with a user defined schedule, which can be daily, weekly, monthly, or yearly. Notification is triggered for both schema and crosswalk whenever a new revision (see "Content management - versioning") is added. Crosswalk notification is also triggered whenever a new revision is created for either source or target schema. This way the maintainer of the crosswalk can stay informed about the changes to schemas that might also require a new revision of the crosswalk.

More information about how to use notification system via the API and through the UI is available in the user guide.

3.4 MSCR features/requirements not included in the final release, further development needs

Support for operationalisation for more combinations of schemas

MSCR does not support operationalisation support for all possible format combinations. The supported set of format pairs were selected based on the project's demonstrator and use case requirements and some important ones might have been omitted.

Support for more schema language features

MSCR does not support all the features of the supported schema formats. In order to improve the registration of existing schemas, further development is needed in schema specification format parsing and transformation. Further development is especially required for XSD, and JSON Schema parsers, as both formats are used extensively for older content. The challenge with XSD is the complexity of the specification. JSON Schema on the other hand has multiple different versions in active use with slightly different vocabularies and semantics.

Add support for more formats

Although the range of formats covered by the MSCR is already quite extensive, there are formats that should be added to the list. During the project there were multiple requests from external testers for a JSON-LD support. A minimal implementation could be for example support for JSON-LD contexts, which could be used as vocabularies for semantic mappings and added to data mappings with JSON output for RDF generation.

Automatically generated mapping suggestions

Right now creating MSCR crosswalks is a purely manual process, but there are multiple potential avenues for the development of automated and semi-automated mapping generation. Mapping suggestions could be generated by querying the MSCR mapping knowledge graph for existing mappings and semantic links between source and target properties. The underlying graph could also be used to validate existing mappings based on their semantics. Another interesting path for further development is the use of AI technologies, large language models and RAGs to generate initial mappings and suggest new mappings.

Guest editors

During the project the need for different permission modes was extended with a scenario that called for restricted write rights to a crosswalk. A guest editor would be able to make changes to a crosswalk content but would not be able to delete drafts or change the state. This case is not supported by the current authorisation framework, but it could be implemented by extending the internal metadata model to include a list of guest editor that is editable by users with normal EDITOR role.

Commenting

The original idea was to use the commenting feature of the Finnish Interoperability Platform without any modification with the MSCR. It turned out that the commenting functionality based on the original

implementation was not well suited to the requirements of the use cases. A more light-weight (possibly annotation based) commenting feature would work better with MSCR content types and could utilise existing annotation services for comment storage.

Performance optimisations

Testing with large schemas such as schema.org and TEI⁹ has shown that larger schemas are slow to load to the UI and some very large schemas even fail to load because of the time it takes to process them. These problems are caused by the fact that MSCR tries to materialise all possible schema node combinations and some of that is currently done at runtime (on-demand). A simple performance optimisation would be to add caching to certain API endpoints for published content that does not change. Other more complicated measures are needed to handle large schemas where the MSCR generated schema model can grow to hundreds of megabytes.

3.5 Access, license, GDPR, source code, user documentation

All code related to the MSCR and Vocabulary service is available in Github under EUPL-1.1 license.

Repositories:

- mscr-datamodel-api - <https://github.com/CSCfi/mscr-datamodel-api>
 - o Main backend repository
- mscr-ui-monorepo - <https://github.com/CSCfi/mscr-ui-monorepo>
 - o Main frontend repository
- mscr-messaging-api - <https://github.com/CSCfi/mscr-messaging-api>
 - o MSCR fork of the original message-api
- mscr-terminology-api - <https://github.com/CSCfi/mscr-terminology-api>
 - o MSCR fork of the original terminology-api

User documentation for the MSCR and vocabulary service is maintained under <https://github.com/CSCfi/mscr-docs> repository and published using Github pages at <https://cscfi.github.io/mscr-docs/>.

3.6 Engagement and dissemination activities undertaken to improve and promote MSCR

EUNIS - European University Information Systems organization

A paper titled "Implementing interoperability - Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry approach to FAIR metadata mappings" (Kesäniemi et al., 2025) was published as part of the proceedings of the EUNIS 2024 conference. The Paper was presented at the EUNIS 2024 conference which provided an international audience from the Higher Education Institutions (HEI) to hear and read how MSCR could be used in their domain.

EuroCRIS

EuroCRIS organises the annual CRIS conference with the aim of enhancing the availability and accessibility of research information systems across Europe. MSCR was presented as part of the CRIS2024 pre-conference organised in collaboration with the RIS Synergy project at the University of Vienna. The workshop included presentations as well as marketplace session where participants were able to interact with the developers of the services and ask questions. A paper was co-authored with EuroCRIS participants

⁹ https://www.tei-c.org/release/xml/tei/custom/schema/xsd/tei_all.xsd

titled "CRIS systems integration as a case study for the Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry" (Kesäniemi et al., 2024) and published in the proceedings of CRIS2024 conference.

BioDT

A Conference abstract titled "Making Schemas and Mappings Available and FAIR: A metadata and schema crosswalk registry from the FAIRCORE4EOSC project" (Suominen, Kesäniemi, et al., 2023) was co-authored with BioDT and presented at the TDWG 2023 conference and published in the Biodiversity Information Science and Standards journal.

FAIR-IMPACT

MSCR participated in the Austrian FAIR National Roadshow series organized by FAIR-Impact as part of the presentation titled "Metadata, semantics and interoperability".

EOSC

MSCR and the Vocabulary Service were promoted and introduced as part of the EOSC Winter School 2024.

FWO Scientific Research Network

Results of the collaboration with SWITCH were presented as part of an event called "Knowledge Graphs for Data Integration" in a presentation titled "MSCR and RDF Mapping Generation: Managing Crosswalks for OpenAlex".

Research Data Alliance (RDA)

RDA is a global community of more than 14000 people from 152 countries that focuses on the development of infrastructure and community activities that lower the barrier for sharing and exchange of research and other data. Member of the MSCR development team were involved with a setting up of a new RDA working group called "FAIR Mappings". The working group was officially endorsed in February 2025 and it is co-chaired by members of the MSCR team and the FAIR-Impact project. Mappings related work within the RDA started more than a year before the official endorsement of the group with MSCR being promoted and discussed in sessions hosted during RDA plenaries P21 (October 2023), P22 (May 2024), P23 (November 2024), and P24 (April 2025).

3.7 User community reception and adoption

Demonstrators

Demonstrators with a small and well-defined scope provided an essential feedback during the development. The results of FAIRCORE4EOSC demonstrators are described in more details in section 4.5.

Case studies

MSCR was part of multiple case studies where the use cases included schema and crosswalk registration, crosswalk creation and transformation of metadata using artefacts generated by the MSCR. All the case studies had a clear understanding how a service like MSCR could improve their operating environments. However, the main challenges for integration revolved around the sustainability of the service and delivery of the most complex features of the MSCR such as support for variety of mappings and operationalization. See Deliverable D7.2 (Elbers et al., 2025) for a detailed description of the case studies.

FAIR-Impact

MSCR and the Vocabulary Service were part of the "Managing data types, schemas and vocabularies and crosswalks for FAIR researcher related metadata " support action, together with the DTR. The support action had around 30 participants from 10 different organisations. The MSCR team helped to organise six

workshops and multiple office hour sessions and provided support via a chat channel. The participating organisations each had a real case to work on, and they had not previous experience with any of the services.

SWITCH

SWITCH foundation's mission is to enable, maintain and promote a secure and networked research and education infrastructure in Switzerland. The MSCR team worked with SWITCH especially on the RML generator and other RDF related issues. MSCR's mapping and data transformation capabilities were tested and developed with concrete use cases from the connectome project. The existing mapping implementation based on RML was used as the benchmark to test MSCR's features. In the first phase, we were able to produce a working crosswalk between the OpenAlex json document schema and a publication related subset of the graph schema (SHACL) used by SWITCH. Validation of the results was done using the RML mapping file generated from the MSCR, which was successfully used to transform OpenAlex JSON documents into RDF. Another experiment that was successfully complemented was the crosswalk and data transformation between OpenAlex json documents and SemOpenAlex RDF graph data. This implementation contributed some new mapping functions to the MSCR that can be used to generate complex URI structures based on the source document.

FAIRSharing

Based on discussions related to synergies between MSCR and FAIRSharing services a loose integration between the two services was planned and implemented with results published in a joint blog post.

3.8 Sustainability of developed service

The MSCR a global open accessible service is maintained after the project by the CSC. The service uses B2Access authentication provider and mints its persistent identifiers through a handle service provided by the GWDG. Further details can be found in the upcoming FAIRCORE4EOSC D7.3 (upcoming, 2025).

3.9 Future developments

Regarding more technical aspect of the MSCR, the demonstrators and case studies have shown that the creation, utilisation and maintenance of crosswalks require collaboration between different stakeholders. The current MSCR provides basic features for collaborative crosswalk related work, but more development is needed to make MSCR more appealing to users. Users outside of the formal demonstrator and case studies have also come up with good candidates for new schema and crosswalk format to be supported.

After the project the main challenge will be related to gaining traction from the different user communities including people working as researchers, data stewards, repository managers and research data related develops that are dealing with schema and crosswalk content on regular basis as well as people responsible for designing data related processes and making decisions on data integrations. This will require active promotion of the MSCR service and success in new implementation case coming outside of the project.

4 Task 4.3 EOSC Data Type Registry

Task 4.3 EOSC Data Type Registry

Lead: GWDG

Participants: SURF, CLARIN, GRNET, AGH/AGH-UST

- **Develop and establish guidelines to ensure interoperability between Data Type registries;**
- **Develop and establish the EOSC DTR as a service (GWDG hosting organisation);**

- **Develop guidelines for communities to register and maintain data types in the EOSC DTR;**
- **Develop APIs for importing and accessing data types;**
- **Develop and register actionable mappings for encodings used with related metadata or data values based on DTR technology;**
- **Develop and establish the EOSC Profile Registry with GWDG as hosting organization;**
- **Align Data Type registration process and governance with the EOSC Provider and Resource onboarding process;**
- **Integrate the DTR with the EOSC-Core services (e.g. Provider Portal, Marketplace and RDGraph)**

Key service info for the EOSC Data Type Registry (DTR)

- **Production Release: Yes, 31-03-2025**
- **Stable Software Release: Yes, 31-03-2025**
- **Agreement documents:**
 - Privacy statement: <https://gwdg.de/en/data-protection-notice/>
 - Terms of Use (ToU): <https://gwdg.de/en/about-us/catalog/terms-and-conditions/terms-of-use/>
 - **Service Level Specifications (SLS):**
 - **Acceptable Use Policy (AUP):**
- **User Documentation: Yes, <https://fc4e-t4-3.github.io/> (planned to be updated 31-05-2025)**
- **Interoperability Guidelines: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15512887>**
- **Code properly Published/Archived: <https://github.com/FC4E-T4-3/type-api>**
- **Integration with EOSC Innovation Sandbox: AAI**

4.1 Introduction and Goals

The Data Type Registry (DTR) is a key service developed as part of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. It provides a framework for the registration, discovery, and management of structured data type definitions. The DTR enables communities to define and publish reusable, machine-readable data types, thereby supporting better data interoperability and reuse in line with the FAIR principles.

The registry is built on top of CNRI's Cordra platform¹⁰ (Tupelo-Schneck, 2022), which offers a robust infrastructure for managing digital objects. Each data type is represented as a digital object, described in JSON, and assigned a persistent identifier (PID). This approach ensures that type definitions are not only structured, but also globally addressable and resolvable over time.

The core goal of the DTR is to offer a sustainable, open service that supports the long-term curation and referencing of data type definitions. It is designed to help data providers ensure that their data structures are well-documented and can be easily understood and reused by others. At the same time, it facilitates discovery and validation by researchers, developers, and service providers who require standardized ways of interpreting data.

The registry is complemented by additional software components, such as the TypeAPI, and is supported by clear governance and interoperability guidelines. These elements together form a complete ecosystem that addresses the technical, organizational, and semantic challenges of managing data types across distributed research infrastructures.

¹⁰ <https://www.cordra.org/>

4.2 Previous Developments

The concept of a Data Type Registry is not new. It builds on over a decade of work, starting with a Research Data Alliance (RDA) working group that laid out a foundational conceptual framework as early as 2014¹¹. That initial work identified the need for a registry of persistent, machine-readable type definitions to promote data reuse and interoperability across domains.

Subsequent endeavours have begun to put these ideas into practice. One notable example was an implementation maintained by the Gesellschaft für wissenschaftliche Datenverarbeitung mbH Göttingen (GWDG), which provided a working instance of a DTR based on early specifications. These efforts served as proof of concept, showing that such a registry could be technically feasible and practically useful.

The FAIRCORE4EOSC project builds on this legacy, formalizing the model and addressing limitations in earlier implementations. It introduces additional tools to streamline the creation, registration, and validation of type definitions, along with improvements in usability, scalability, and governance. Also, it expands the registry beyond schema elements to additional, useful elements for research. As a result, the current version of the DTR is a fully functional, interoperable, and reproducible service that can be integrated into a broader research ecosystem.

4.3 Technical Foundation

The DTR is implemented as a modular system built on proven technologies, designed to ensure scalability, extensibility, and ease of integration with other services within the EOSC ecosystem. Its architecture consists of several core components that work together to support the full lifecycle of data type definitions, from creation and registration to discovery and validation.

The system is designed to accommodate a wide variety of use cases. Whether through graphical user interfaces for manual type creation or APIs for automated workflows, the DTR supports both human- and machine-oriented interactions.

The following subsections provide a detailed breakdown of the main technical components that constitute the DTR architecture.

4.3.1 Components and Architecture

The architecture of the DTR is designed to be modular and extensible, allowing various components to interact seamlessly while maintaining clear responsibilities. The system leverages established technologies to ensure persistence, scalability, and flexibility in managing structured data types.

Each data type in the registry is treated as a digital object, managed within the Cordra platform. These objects are assigned persistent identifiers, versioned, and stored with structured metadata. The system supports REST and DOIP APIs, providing both human-friendly and programmatic access to type definitions. On top of this core, the TypeAPI as additional service enhances the registry's capabilities for schema generation, federated discovery, and validation.

For a diagram displaying the general structure and an overview, refer to Figure 6 in the section for task 4.1, covering requirements, specifications, and integration.

¹¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-type-registries-wg/outputs/?output=94741>

Cordra Platform

The Cordra platform serves as the backbone of the DTR infrastructure. It is a highly adaptable system for managing JSON-based digital objects, each of which is identified by a persistent identifier registered through the Handle system. Cordra was selected for its robust support for PID management and customizable object modelling.

Within the context of the DTR, Cordra has been extended with custom schemas tailored to data type definitions. These schemas allow for rich metadata descriptions, constraints, and hierarchical structures. The platform supports built-in authentication and authorization, enabling role-based access control and ownership assignment. Users can manage visibility and editing rights at the object level, making it suitable for both public and restricted type definitions as well as ownership on an organization level.

Cordra also provides interfaces for automated workflows, with token-based authentication for secure interactions via its REST API. These features collectively make it a powerful base for building a persistent and interoperable registry of reusable data types.

Figure 16: Cordra Architecture Overview

TypeAPI

To support advanced functionality such as schema generation, validation, and federated discovery, the DTR includes a dedicated service called the **TypeAPI**. This component is implemented as a RESTful web service using **Spring Boot version 2.6**¹², ensuring a modern and maintainable backend framework. For indexing and caching, the TypeAPI utilizes **TypeSense version 2.5**¹³, a high-performance search engine optimized for structured data.

The TypeAPI extends the capabilities of the DTR beyond simple object storage by providing programmatic access to type definitions in a format suitable for schema processing and automated workflows. One of its core functions is the transformation of DTR type descriptions into **JSON Schema**, which allows developers and services to validate data instances against a formally defined structure. This validation can be executed directly via the API using the persistent identifier (PID) of a registered type.

¹² <https://spring.io/>

¹³ <https://typesense.org/>

Technically, the TypeAPI exposes endpoints for retrieving full schema definitions, generating validation rules on-the-fly, and submitting JSON documents for conformity checks. It also supports advanced filtering of type definitions based on metadata fields, taxonomy classifications, or hierarchical relationships.

Furthermore, the API is designed to accommodate **federated deployments**, meaning it can interact with and index multiple remote DTR instances, provided they adhere to a supported schema and the interoperability guidelines. This federation is essential for cross-registry search, comparison, and reuse of data types.

In short, the TypeAPI operationalizes much of the logic that underpins the DTR and makes its contents actionable - whether by humans browsing a frontend or services consuming type metadata in automated pipelines.

Figure 17: The TypeAPI Architecture

4.3.2 Features available in Release

The release version of the DTR delivers a comprehensive set of features that support the end-to-end lifecycle of data type management—from creation and metadata enrichment to access control, validation, and discovery. These features are accessible through both the web-based user interface and the underlying REST API, allowing flexibility for various user roles and technical capabilities.

Type Creation and Management

Users can begin by creating new data types through an intuitive web interface. The process is guided by a step-by-step workflow that helps users select an appropriate base schema, provide core metadata such as name and description, and define type-specific properties. These properties can include structured fields, constraints, and value domains, depending on the needs of the specific data context. Users may also assign measurement units and link types to taxonomy nodes for categorization and semantic clarity.

Versioning is fully supported, allowing users to specify version numbers, and link current types to previous or next versions. This ensures traceability and allows applications to track the evolution of type definitions over time.

For those integrating the DTR into automated workflows, the system provides a robust programmatic interface via Cordra’s REST API. This interface allows applications to authenticate using token-based

mechanisms, retrieve type definitions using persistent identifiers, create or update types by submitting structured JSON objects, and perform advanced search operations based on metadata filters or taxonomy-based queries.

Authentication and Authorization

To ensure secure access and controlled collaboration, the DTR implements a robust authentication and authorization framework. This system supports both individual user authentication and fine-grained permission management for registered types.

Authentication is handled through integration with established federated identity providers. Specifically, the DTR supports login via the **EOSC Innovation Sandbox**, which is currently available as a beta version, and the **Academic Cloud AAI**, which allow users to authenticate using their institutional credentials. This federation of identities promotes seamless access across services and reduces the administrative burden of managing separate user accounts.

Once authenticated, users are able to perform operations in accordance with their assigned roles and permissions. The DTR supports detailed access control mechanisms, allowing type owners to define who can view, edit, or manage each type. Access rights can be granted to individual users or to user groups, enabling collaborative editing and controlled dissemination within projects or institutions.

In addition to permission settings, the platform includes functionality for **ownership transfer**. A user who initially registers a type may assign its ownership to another user, thereby transferring responsibility for future maintenance. This is particularly useful in institutional settings where roles may change over time, or where the long-term stewardship of types needs to be formalized.

Together, these authentication and authorization features ensure that data type definitions are not only secure and traceable but also adaptable to dynamic organizational structures and collaborative workflows.

Schema Generation and Data Validation

A central feature of the DTR component is its ability to translate data type definitions into machine-readable validation schemas. This functionality is primarily powered by the TypeAPI, which serves as the bridge between human-authored type descriptions and formalized, actionable schemas in the JSON Schema standard.

When a user defines a type in the DTR - by specifying fields, constraints, and associated metadata - the TypeAPI can generate a corresponding JSON schema that precisely reflects this structure. This schema can then be used by external applications and services to validate actual data instances, ensuring that they conform to the expectations laid out in the type definition.

Validation is performed by submitting a JSON object alongside the persistent identifier (PID) of the target type. The TypeAPI retrieves the schema associated with the PID and applies it to the data object, returning clear feedback on any mismatches or violations. This enables automated data quality checks, both within and beyond the scope of the DTR itself.

The process is designed to be lightweight and API-driven, making it easy to embed within data workflows, pipelines, and third-party tools. Whether validating research metadata, experimental results, or repository submissions, the DTR ensures that structural correctness and semantic coherence can be verified programmatically and consistently.

By offering native support for schema generation and validation, the DTR supports FAIR data practices - not just through human-readable documentation, but by providing the technical foundations needed for machine-actionable interoperability.

Registerable Types

The DTR supports a wide range of type categories, each designed to fulfill a distinct role in the description and structuring of data. This categorization ensures that different use cases - from defining basic elements to modelling complex metadata profiles - are appropriately supported within a consistent framework.

At the core of the system are **BasicInfoTypes**, which represent the most fundamental building blocks. These types typically correspond to simple, atomic structures, such as strings, numerical values, or controlled lists of values. They provide a foundation upon which more complex types can be constructed.

Building on these are **InfoTypes**, which describe either homogeneous or heterogeneous collections of data types. These types are flexible in design and are intended to model richer structures that can combine multiple fields, relationships, and constraints.

To address the need for comprehensive, standards-aligned metadata representations, the DTR also supports **Profiles**. These are composite types that aggregate other types - including BasicInfoTypes and InfoTypes - into a cohesive unit. Profiles are typically used to define full metadata records for data objects, services, or workflows, and may conform to community or disciplinary standards.

In addition to content types, the DTR allows users to define and register **Taxonomy Nodes**. These nodes enable the construction of hierarchical classification systems, which can be used to group, organize, or filter other types semantically. Taxonomy nodes play a critical role in discovery, allowing users to browse and explore types based on conceptual relationships.

For quantitative data, the DTR provides a straightforward mechanism for registering **Measurement Units**. These units can then be assigned to schema elements, facilitating consistent interpretation and comparison of numerical values across datasets.

Finally, the DTR includes a registry of **Extended MIME Types**, which builds upon the official IANA Media Types¹⁴. By assigning persistent identifiers and enriching them with additional metadata, the DTR makes these media types more actionable in automated environments, supporting enhanced content negotiation and semantic resolution.

Together, these registerable categories offer a flexible and extensible vocabulary for modeling data across diverse scientific domains, while ensuring consistency, discoverability, and interoperability within and beyond the registry.

4.3.3 Integrations

One key area of integration is with **federated identity providers**, namely the **EOSC AAI**¹⁵ and the **Academic Cloud AAI**¹⁶. These integrations ensure that users can authenticate using their institutional credentials, maintaining security and consistency across services while minimizing the need for additional account management.

¹⁴ <https://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml>

¹⁵ <https://docs.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/Service%20Portfolio/AAI/AAI/>

¹⁶ https://docs.gwdg.de/doku.php?id=de:services:general_services:academicid:start

In addition to identity management, the DTR can interact with the **FAIRCORE4EOSC Vocabulary Service**. This integration allows data type definitions to reference standardized terminologies and controlled vocabularies registered in the vocabulary service, helping to ensure semantic coherence and enabling meaningful comparisons between types across disciplines.

These integrations are not only technical in nature but are also strategically aligned to foster a rich, interoperable research infrastructure. By embedding itself within this ecosystem, the DTR becomes more than just a standalone tool - it aims to serve as a foundational service that supports the FAIRification of data and metadata across domains.

4.4 Schemas

The DTR's ability to register and manage diverse types is underpinned by a well-defined and consistent schema model. This model ensures that all registered types are described using a common structural foundation while allowing for the flexibility needed to accommodate different domains and use cases. Schemas in the DTR are themselves structured digital objects, designed for both human readability and machine usability.

4.4.1 General Schema Structure

All data type definitions registered in the DTR follow a standardized schema structure that captures both technical and descriptive metadata. Each schema includes a set of core fields that establish the identity, provenance, and contextual use of the type.

Table 12: General schema structure

Index	Name	Type	Cardinality	Description
1	Name	String	1	The name of the type
2	Description	String	0 - 1	A detailed description of the type
3	Versioning	Object	0 - 1	Object containing version information
3.1	Version	String	0 - 1	The current version string
3.2	PreviousVersion	String	0 - 1	Reference to the previous version (PID)
3.3	NextVersion	String	0 - 1	Reference to the next version (PID)
4	Provenance	Object	1	Object containing information about the type's origin
4.1	Contributors	Object	0 - n	Array of contributors with name and optional ORCID
4.1.1	Name	String	0 - 1	
4.1.2	ORCID	String	0 - 1	
4.2	CreationDate	String	1	Timestamp of creation
4.3	LastModificationDate	String	1	Timestamp of last modification
5	ExpectedUse	String	0 - 1	Description of how and in what context the type should be used
6	References	String	0 - n	A list of internal and external references
7	Aliases	String	0 - n	Array of alternative names for the type

8	TaxonomyNodes	String	0 - n	List of Taxonomy Nodes (PID)
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4.4.2 Type specific properties

Beyond the shared metadata model, each data type may define its own specific properties—these are the elements that constitute the type’s schema in practical terms.

The specific extensions to the general base schema that are used to define schema elements will be focused on here.

For BasicInfoTypes:

Table 13: BasicInfoType schema structure

Index	Name	Type	Cardinality	Description
1	Type	String	1	The fundamental type (String, Number, Boolean, Enum)
2	Relations between Properties	String	0 - 1	Optional boolean options between properties (AND, OR, XOR)
3	Properties	Object	0 - n	Container for set of properties
3.1	Property	String	1	Type specific property (e.g. minLength)
3.2	Value	Any	1	Value for the respective property

For InfoTypes and Profiles, if they represent objects:

Table 14: InfoType/Profile object schema structure

Index	Name	Type	Cardinality	Description
1	Type	String	1	Object
2	AdditionalProperties	Boolean	0 - 1	If the resulting schema should allow additional properties
3	SubschemaCondition	String	0 - 1	Specify anyOf, allOf, or oneOf
4	Property	Object	0 - n	Container for the set of properties
4.1	Name	String	1	Name of the property
4.2	Title	String	0 - 1	Optional title for the JSON schema
4.3	Description	String	0 - 1	Optional description for the schema
4.4	Type	PID	1	Reference to the described type
4.4	Const	Any	0 - 1	Optional const value for the property
4.5	Cardinality	String	1	Describe the cardinality of the property (0, 0-1, 1, 1-n)
4.6	ExtractProperties	Boolean	0 - 1	Optional, advanced field for schema generation

For InfoTypes, representing arrays:

Table 15: InfoType array schema structure

Index	Name	Type	Cardinality	Description
1	Type	String	1	Object
2	Description	String	0 - 1	Optional description for the schema
3	Type	PID	1	Reference to the described type
4	Uniqueltems	Boolean	0 - 1	If only optional elements must be present
5	MinItems	Integer	0 - 1	Minimum number of elements
6	MaxItems	Integer	0 - 1	Maximum number of elements

4.5 Access, license, GDPR, source code, user documentation

The DTR and its components are openly available and maintained. The **TypeAPI** is released under the **MIT License** and can be accessed via GitHub at github.com/FC4E-T4-3/type-api.

User documentation is published at fc4e-t4-3.github.io, covering usage guidance, API examples, and integration notes. The **JSON schemas** used for type definitions are versioned and hosted at github.com/FC4E-T4-3/schemas.

The service is designed with **GDPR compliance** in mind, minimizing personal data collection.

4.6 Engagement and dissemination activities undertaken to improve and promote DTR

EuroCRIS

EuroCRIS organized an annual CRIS conference with the aim of enhancing the availability and accessibility of research information systems across Europe. The DTR was presented as part of the CRIS2024 pre-conference organized in collaboration with the RIS Synergy project at the University of Vienna. The workshop included presentations as well as marketplace session where participants were able to interact with the developers of the services and ask questions.

FAIR-Impact

The DTR was part of the "Managing data types, schemas and vocabularies and crosswalks for FAIR researcher related metadata " support action in collaboration with the MSCR and the vocabulary service. The support action has around 30 participants from 10 different organizations. The DTR team helped to organize six workshops, multiple office hour sessions and provided support via a chat channel. The participating organizations each had a real case to work on and they had not previously been involved in service development

4.7 User community reception

(this may be a summary, as outputs of T4.5 or Case studies don't need to be repeated here, pointers are enough. When this deliverable is published D7.2 will be out and published.

4.8 Sustainability of developed service

To ensure mid-term sustainability, instances of the DTR and the TypeAPI will be hosted by **GWDG** under the **ePIC governance**. This ensures continued availability, maintenance, and integration support beyond the lifetime of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

The open-source nature of the components, along with their alignment with established standards and EOSC services, further contributes to their ongoing relevance and adaptability, and allows other organizations to host their own DTR instance.

4.9 Future development

Several enhancements are envisioned to extend the capabilities and reach of the DTR. These include deeper integration with other **EOSC services**, allowing for more seamless data exchange and interoperability across the research ecosystem.

To improve usability, future work may focus on **visualizing type hierarchies** and relationships, providing clearer insight into dependencies and semantic groupings. Finally, **expanded federation capabilities** and the development of a **custom frontend** for the federated service are planned, allowing visual exploration across multiple DTR instances.

5 Task 4.4 EOSC Research Activity Identifier Service

Task 4.4 EOSC Research Activity Identifier Service

Lead: SURF

Participants: GRNET, AGH/AGH-UST, ARDC

- Organise a RAiD PID systems working group to implement agreed PID to PID interaction and metadata alignment.
- Align with RAiD development efforts within the FAIR Implementation Workflows Project (funded by the Templeton World Charity Foundation) and the ongoing developments by ARDC
- Establish EOSC/European RAiD registry (SURF hosting organization)
- Define EOSC RAiD and project information framework; Integrate RAiD into existing EOSC service catalogue processes.
- Incorporate priority PIDs (e.g. RAiD, ORCID, RoR, Grant ID) in EOSC service utilization workflow(s).

Key service info for the EOSC Research Activity Identifier service (RAiD)

- **Production Release: Yes, 31-01-2025** operated by ARDC, in beta stage operated by SURF
- **Stable Software Release: Yes, 31-01-2025**
- **Agreement documents:**
 - **Service Level Specification (SLS):** <https://github.com/au-research/raido/blob/main/doc/service-level-guide.md>
 - **Acceptable Use Policy (AUP): Model service policy:** <https://documentation.ardc.edu.au/raid/raid-service-policy>, to be adapted by SURF and other RAiD Registration Agencies

- **Terms of Use (ToU):**
- **Privacy Statement (DPS):**
- User Documentation: <https://documentation.raid.org/raid/?l=en>
- **Interoperability Guidelines:**
 - **For new Service Endpoints:** <https://documentation.raid.org/raid/register-as-a-new-service-point>
- Metadata schema: <https://metadata.raid.org/en/latest/>
- **Code properly Published/Archived:** <https://github.com/au-research/raid-au>
- **Integration with EOSC Innovation Sandbox: No**

5.1 Introduction to RAiD development

The RAiD (Research Activity Identifier) provides a unique, persistent identifier for research projects, enabling clear and consistent discovery, reporting, and communication. As a global registry, RAiD brings together all relevant project information into standardized metadata records, supporting version control, multi-party access, and the creation of an automatic landing page for each project. As projects have many forms that can evolve over time, RAiD accommodates a wide range of project configurations, such as projects with multiple funding sources and/or large complex projects that are better represented by multiple linked RAiDs. By tracking resources, inputs, and outputs over time, RAiD facilitates comprehensive reporting and assessment, offering valuable strategic insights into project progress, outcomes, and impact.

Early discussions about including RAiD in the FAIRCORE4EOSC proposal took place while ARDC was transitioning RAiD from a local Australian service to a globally scalable one. At the time, RAiD was operating as a pilot across several Australian universities, primarily functioning as a project identifier without a comprehensive metadata schema. Prior to defining requirements for EOSC RAiD, ARDC had made limited progress toward a global implementation. The original pilot version, which existed before 2022, was entirely discarded, with no reuse of its code.

Development under the FAIRCORE4EOSC project has included the creation of a new global RAiD service, the establishment of a RAiD Registration Agency to deliver EOSC RAiD services, and a proof-of-concept integration with EOSC infrastructure. This redevelopment effort has simultaneously addressed two core objectives: building a globally capable RAiD system and setting up a RAiD Registration Agency at SURF to support delivery within the EOSC ecosystem.

A key component of this development was the formation of the RAiD Advisory Group, established by ARDC. This group provided strategic guidance on technical development, community adoption, governance, and RAiD's positioning within the broader persistent identifier (PID) ecosystem. It also supported the transition of RAiD to a global capability and identified external factors that could influence its success. Among other topics, the group addressed PID-to-PID interactions and metadata alignment. The FAIRCORE4EOSC project is represented in the Advisory Group by two project partners.

5.2 Development Activities

5.2.1 RAiD Features/ requirements included in the final release

The Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) system has made significant progress, with approximately 75% of planned FAIRCORE4EOSC features now fully implemented. Core functionality is operational in production, including comprehensive search capabilities across all Registration Agencies. The metadata schema has been documented and implemented, and integration with key PID services such as DataCite and ORCID has

been completed. The system architecture successfully supports federation across multiple Registration Agencies (RAs), with SURF Netherlands established as the first international RA alongside ARDC Australia.

Global search functionality and cross-RA data access have been successfully completed, enabling unified discovery across the federated RAiD ecosystem. Implementation of granular user roles and permissions has also been finalised, providing appropriate access controls across the system. Current development priorities include performance optimisation, expanding API functionality, and enhancing specific metadata management features. A small number of requirements have been rejected as redundant or out of scope, while others such as advanced PID validation have been deferred to future development phases.

The RAiD system has successfully achieved its core mission of providing persistent identifiers for research projects that connect organisations, people, and outputs. With its ISO standard governance (ISO, 2022) and expanding global footprint, RAiD has established itself as a key component of the global research information infrastructure, effectively reducing administrative burden and enhancing research transparency.

Completed Development

Core RAiD functionality

- RAiD creation and editing via both API and GUI
- RAiD resolution (returning metadata when a known RAiD identifier is resolved)
- API services for RAiD operations including creating, editing, and resolving
- DataCite DOI implementation as RAiD identifier
- Support for related RAiDs with various named relationships
- Landing page implementation for resolved RAiDs
- GUI user interface implementation following good UI/UX practices

Metadata management

- Metadata schema v1.0 implementation with documentation
- Support for versioning of RAiD metadata
- Controlled vocabularies published through Research Vocabularies Australia
- Support for "extended" metadata elements customized by Registration Agencies
- Implementation of time-limited embargoes for RAiDs with (temporarily) sensitive metadata
- Tracking and display of RAiD metadata change history for authenticated users

Authentication and access

- Multiple login methods implemented, (AAF, ORCID, Google, EduGAIN)
- Implementation of granular user roles and permissions
- Basic role-based access with Service Point Admin and user roles; RAiD administrator and user roles
- Ability to elevate Service Point user to Service Point administrator via web application
- Support for creating and managing Service Points via web application
- Ability to move user from one Service Point to another via web application

Integration and Interoperability

- ORCID integration with automated update of ORCID from RAiD
- Integration with DataCite for DOI minting, partial metadata discovery, and inclusion in DataCite's PIDGraph
- Validation of external PIDs (proper formatting; resolvable)
- PID resolution via PIDMR (PID Metadata Registry)

- Integration with RDGraph

Deployment, administration, and federation

- Scripts for automated deployment to AWS (some transferable to other environments)
- Service Point management for Registration Agencies
- Daily JSON data dumps for bulk access to RAiD metadata (per instance)
- Quarterly JSON dumps published to Zenodo (per instance)
- Global search functionality across all Registration Agencies
- Cross-RA search and data access

Documentation

- API documentation using Swagger
- Metadata schema documentation

Infrastructure

- AWS deployment model with containerization
- GitHub repositories for code and documentation
- Collaborative development framework established between ARDC and SURF

5.2.2 RAiD Features/requirements not included in the final release, further development needs

Pending Development

- Search by various metadata elements (Organisation, Service Point, etc.)
- Performance optimisation for bulk operations
- API endpoint for RAiD change history
- Additional RAiD management service improvements
- Enhancement of Service Point management for Registration Agencies
- Implementation of embargoed metadata access rules
- Further interoperability with external PID services
- Additional performance optimizations
- More comprehensive API search functionality
- User-facing documentation
- Registration Agency documentation

Postponed Development

- Additional validation of external PIDs with originating services
- Automated bi-directional updates between RAiD and additional PID services
- Other automated PID interactions
- Improved metadata embargo management
- Enhanced reporting capabilities based on aggregate RAiD data
- Additional performance optimisations for scaling to hundreds of thousands of RAiDs and managing large RAiDs (i.e., RAiDs with hundreds of components)

Rejected Development

- Permanent confidentiality of RAiD metadata (only time-limited embargoes supported)
- Certain complex harvesting and PID graph integration scenarios
- Redundant approaches to metadata schema implementation

Technical Notes

1. **Duplications:** Several issues were identified as duplicates during development. These have been consolidated in this report.
2. **Architecture:** The RAiD service architecture allows for federation across multiple Registration Agencies while maintaining a common core metadata schema.
3. **DataCite partnership:** The implementation uses DataCite DOIs as the underlying identifier infrastructure for RAiD, with partial metadata deposited in DataCite systems to enable PIDGraph integration.
4. **Access model:** The system uses a hierarchical access model with Registration Authorities, Registration Agencies, Service Points, and users.
5. **Performance:** Service level expectations have been documented, with additional performance optimization ongoing.

5.2.3 Access, license, GDPR, source code, user documentation

- Access to the SURF RAiD instance is granted through the EOSC AAI, the national (NL) AAI service SURFConext and via direct access (account registration) to the system via KeyCloak: <https://www.keycloak.org>, (<https://servicedesk.surf.nl/wiki/spaces/IAM/pages/74220053/SURFconext>)
- The RAiD source code is available publicly on GitHub: <https://github.com/au-research/raid-au>
- Documentation from SURF
- SURF-hosted [knowledge base](#) for API operations, not public yet, it will be made available when the SURF instance will be in production <https://servicedesk.surf.nl/wiki/spaces/WIKI/pages/1474609/SURF+User+Knowledge+Base>
- SURF instance - Swagger UI at <https://api.raid.surf.nl/swagger-ui/index.html> for the API
- SURF internal documentation on service management (e.g., onboarding of new institutions)
- GDPR compliance is detailed in the data processing agreement compiled at SURF

5.3 Engagement and dissemination activities undertaken to improve and promote RAiD

On the project level, dissemination and engagement activities are documented in the upcoming deliverable ***D7.3 Final Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities***. Strategic alignment activities with different actors are documented in ***D1.5 Strategic Alignment and Contribution to the EOSC Partnership*** (Halonen et al., 2025). Below an excerpt of events where SURF has spread knowledge about RAiD during dissemination activities of various nature: from focused, short webinars to national (NL) and international conferences. Here is a list of events during which RAiD was promoted:

- APAN 59, March 2025, Yokohama (JP) - "Workshop: The crucial role of NRENs in data management and Open Science (RDA)" - introducing RAiD as a new, Open Science-enabling service

- FAIRfest Den Haag, 20-21 February 2025: RAiD poster; [RAiD talk](#) - talking about establishing the RAiD service at SURF in the context of the FC4E project.
- EUDAT conference, 03 December 2024 - FC4E 10 services presentation, RAiD service
- GÉANT [webinar](#) on new Open Science Concepts, November 2024, online - "RAiD, a new PID service in Europe" - introducing RAiD as a new, Open Science-enabling service
- FAIRImpact National Roadshow, October 2024, Den Haag (NL) - "CAT & RAiD: how do these services help the research community?" - Introducing the two FC4E-developed services to the National (NL) audience.
- SURF Research Day, July 2024, Amersfoort (NL) - Exhibition booth with information on RAiD for the national (NL) research community.
- PIDFest, June 2024, Prague (CZ): "NRENs and PIDs: the role of research support organisations in the PID landscape" - Talking about SURF's role as an NREN and as the service provider of RAiD in the EU.
- PIDFest, June 2024, Prague (CZ): "Leveraging PIDs to implement Open Science aware Responsible Research Assessment"
- CRIS2024, pre workshop. Vienna, Austria, 14 May, 2024; Services developed by FAIRCORE4EOSC - Introduction to RAiD
- CRIS2024. Vienna, Austria, May 15-17, 2024 - Piloting RAiD in [Research.fi](#)
- Publication-2024: Piloting the use of RAiD in [Research.fi](#). Procedia Computer Science Volume 249, 2024, Pages 224-231. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.11.068>

Additionally, RAiD has been a common topic of conversation during informal meetings and networking occasions, when talking with data supporters, researchers, funders and other representatives of research communities

5.4 User community reception

For the FAIRCORE4EOSC project we define the EOSC RAiD user community in four segments: (1) RAiD Advisory Group, (2) engagement with potential users at conferences and workshops, (3) project case studies, and (4) SURF pilots. In general, introduction of the RAiD was received with enthusiasm about the perceived potential in organization of project information and the RAiD's fit in the PID landscape. Engaging each of these user segments provided valuable input into the development of RAiD.

(1) The RAiD Advisory Group provided strategic guidance on technical development, community adoption, governance, and RAiD's positioning within the broader persistent identifier (PID) ecosystem. See above in the 'Introduction to RAiD development' section.

(2) Engagement with potential users at conferences and workshops informed potential demand for the EOSC RAiD, expanded the range of EOSC RAiD use cases to consider, and served as an important venue for dissemination. See above in the 'Engagement and dissemination activities' section.

(3) Two FAIRCORE4EOSC case studies included the EOSC RAiD (Climate Change and National Repositories). Both pushed the boundaries of planned use cases of RAiD. The case studies provided early feedback, adding requirements that improved the durability of the RAiD design. See D7.2 for outcomes of these two case studies.

(4) Two pilots, a research institute use case and a university use, were carried out at SURF to inform the RAiD service model. This activity supported development of the RAiD Registration Agency business model. See below, in the 'EOSC RAiD's product lifecycle management' section.

5.5 Sustainability of the service at SURF, a European Registration Agency offering 'EOSC RAiD'

5.5.1 The SURF Registration Agency

SURF and ARDC will launch the SURF Registration Agency in 2025. By means of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, SURF is the first European Registration Agency of RAiD. As such, SURF will offer RAiD to European users by providing access to the new RAiD instance hosted at SURF, called EOSC RAiD. Besides collaborating with ARDC and other institutes to expand the adoption and uptake of RAiD, as the European Registration Agency, SURF manages an instance of the RAiD software, provisions and supports Service Points, and ensures a sustainable business operation for the EOSC RAiD service.

SURF participates in the RAiD Advisory Group to support the global development of RAiD's technical development, community adoption and governance. This participation will continue, while the RAiD Advisory Group also seeks to plan near and mid-term future development and operations of the RAiD service to ensure the service's operation as more Registration Agencies are launched. Registration Agencies will be formalised through the establishment of a Registration Agency Agreement, outlining the agreements between Registration Agencies (such as SURF) and the RAiD Registration Authority (ARDC). This agreement is planned for 2025.

Throughout the duration of the project, SURF has engaged with other institutions within the Netherlands and in Europe to not only generate interest in the RAiD service, but to educate potential users of the service about its value and functionalities. For a service that could potentially change established practices in the open research information ecosystem, it is important that the ecosystem is well prepared for adoption. Understanding this, SURF has initialised projects in national consortia where the exploitation of RAiD will help institutes mature in their research information management, for example when institutes lack structured and centralized tooling for such information management. As SURF is a collaborative of members from multiple sectors, its engagements with research institutes, universities, applied science colleges and medical centres have revealed valuable use cases for RAiD adoption. Further, SURF is working with national funders to align their grant application systems to the RAiD metadata schema — further enabling the landscape for RAiD adoption through standardization of the information ecosystem.

The technical and organisational set-up of the Registration Agency has been driven by a small core service team in collaboration with many teams at SURF. This ensures that the software is set up as a full service having been through a development pipeline with many quality assessments, in concert with engagement activities to prepare institutions for adoption upon release of the EOSC RAiD software. These teams and their core collaborative activities with the core team are illustrated below in **Figure 18. SURF Registration Agency Organisation**.

The organisation can be roughly segmented into 3 lanes: The quality and standards lane filled by SURF's Privacy, Security and Legal teams, then the middle lane representing SURF's services and portfolios by the Portfolio Commission, the core EOSC RAiD Service Team and other Research and Education Services, then the externally-facing SURF Portfolio Advice Commission, Relationship Management and Open Research Information teams. The SURF Portfolio Advice Commission is hosted by SURF's Board of Directors and attended by a delegation of IT representatives from the various sectors composing SURF's membership

Figure 18: SURF Registration Agency organization

5.5.2 The EOSC RAiD instance at hosted at SURF

SURF has redeployed all the RAiD software components by the writing of this report, with exception of the RAiD GUI which is planned for release by the end of the FAIRCORE4EOSC project. SURF has tested the redeployment of RAiD by launching the service on its own infrastructure, made possible by the modularity of the RAiD service components.

Below is an architectural description of SURF’s EOSC RAiD implementation:

- The codebase of RAiD, developed to be deployed on Amazon Web Services (AWS), was adapted to run on SURF's already present infrastructure, with the added benefit of exploring the redeployability of the platform on open-source infrastructure.
- The RAiD instance is accessible via API, which is stable and reliable. The API is being used by case studies and pilots to test the service and by the EOSC Marketplace to integrate the two services. A GUI to interact with the RAiD instance at SURF is currently missing.
- The RAiD instance is connected to a national AAI service (SURFConext), which allows users from Dutch institutions to access the service using their institutional credentials. This is not currently possible with the API-based access, but it will be available through the GUI.

- Authentication to the RAiD instance is managed by KeyCloak, which facilitates integration with other authentication services such as the EOSC AAI.
- Support for EOSC users of the SURF RAiD instance will be provided by the SURF help desk, where users of the EOSC help desk will be redirected.

RAiD is intended to interoperate with other services and understanding how to connect it with project management and information systems is part of the scope of the national pilots that SURF is leading. The initial integration with ORCID as a priority PID demonstrate this capability (see the section Development activities above, for more information about interoperability).

5.5.3 Project information framework

The EOSC Marketplace has been integrated with the RAiD service provided by SURF, enhancing its role as a central access point for research-related tools and identifiers.

- RAiD creation: Logged-in users can create RAiDs through an advanced form designed for usability and strict metadata validation in line with RAiD standards.
- User interface: The RAiD form and listing views have been designed and tested for optimal user experience and accessibility.
- RAiD listing: All created RAiDs are visible in a unified view within the marketplace. The interface is prepared to support ORCID-based filtering once the RAiD API allows it.
- ORCID integration: While not yet active, the system is ready to display RAiDs filtered by the user's ORCID identifier when the feature becomes available.
- Screenshots:
 - RAiD list view (Figure 19.)
 - RAiD Creation Form (Figure 20.)

This integration supports EOSC's goals of research transparency, persistent identifiers, and interoperability.

Figure 19: RAiD list view

Figure 20: RAiD Creation Form

5.5.4 Provisioning and supporting Service Points

To deliver the EOSC RAiD service, SURF can provision Service Points to institutes. This entails providing institutes the following:

- A DOI prefix
- A DataCite repository
- A KeyCloak group based on their institute
- Access to the RAiD API
- Access to the RAiD GUI

In addition to provisioned access to the EOSC RAiD service, SURF offers Service Point users support through its Jira service desk portal and technical consultancy for the service.

The Service Points are key product via which SURF’s EOSC RAiD Service is delivered to end-users. **Figure 21** shows that the Service Points offered to institutes by SURF can then be used by the members of these institutes. While SURF distributes these Service Points as the Registration Agency, collaborates on code enhancement and maintains a sustainable business model, the Service Points manage their own users and integration with the other services in use at their institute. The end users access the RAiD service via their membership to the Service Point, wherein they can mint and manage RAiDs. ARDC acts as the Registration Authority, maintaining the ISO standard, offering redeployment of RAiD, and leading development of the RAiD service globally. Long-term plans are being made to have the code co-developed between the Registration Agencies and ARDC.

Figure 21: Levels of RAiD operations and relevant responsibilities for the organizations involved

5.5.5 EOSC RAiD's product lifecycle management

Development Cycle at SURF

To establish EOSC RAiD as a sustainable service at SURF, the service was subjected to SURF's Lifecycle Product Management (LCPM) process. This process entails various stages of product development, covering technical design, business modelling, privacy, legal and quality controls, and stakeholder inclusion so that the service development is aligned to the concerns of the many institutes in the Netherlands who will fund the operations of the service.

Figure 22. below illustrates the sequential stages of the EOSC RAiD product's development in SURF's LCPM process, from version 0.1 to 1.0. From the left, each phase (at the top) dictates a set of activities (at the bottom) which are checked and controlled via two decision-gates: 1) the review by the portfolio commission which assesses the fit and quality of the service within SURF's service portfolio, and 2) the pitch given to the SURF Portfolio Advice Commission which assesses the fit and quality of the service to the market, represented by key IT stakeholders of the different market segments of the institutions. At the end of each phase, the decision-gates approved the continuation of the service development. However, during a final decision gate of the pilot phase in March 2025, the commission asked that the service be presented again in June 2025, as the representatives were not prepared to make a decision on the service.

Figure 22: EOSC RAiD Lifecycle Product Management at SURF

Value proposition canvas

During the product development process, some activities produced valuable key outputs not only for SURF, but for other organizations who wish to either use RAiD or redeploy RAiD as a new Registration Agency. These mostly include the following outputs:

- Exploration phase: value proposition canvas
- Proof of concept phase: business model
- Pilot phase: pilot use cases

The value proposition canvas segmented end-users by role, defined their pains, and assessed how the service solves these pains. A summary of this analysis can be viewed in **Table 16** below which describes the pains each type of end-user experiences while trying to accomplish their goals, and what they want to gain an advantage in achieving their goals.

Table 16: User pains and gains

	Current pains in their work	Gains to improve their work
Research Administrators	...cannot gather information easily because it is siloed in different systems	...want to access research information quickly, easily and reliably
Researchers/Support Staff	...cannot discover reliable information because a single source of truth is missing	...want to have research information they can trust
Funders	...cannot track outcomes of grants easily because it relies on human reporting which struggles with siloed information	have information readily available for reporting
Research Infra Operators	...cannot track resources and outcomes because systems are not integrated and information becomes unreliable due to manual, duplicate, or missing entry	...want to have information registered and maintained from the beginning of the project
Research Platform Operators	...gather information in an ad-hoc manner, introducing errors and gaps in information tracking/reporting	...want to have project information maintained during project lifespan
Integrators/Harvesters	...cannot rely on information quality; information is not always reliable (bad data quality)	...want to integrate with RAiD to maintain information integrity and availability from source

To address these pains and gains, the value proposition analysis describes how the RAiD service would address these pains and deliver upon these gains (Table 17).

Table 17: Pain relievers and gain creators

Pain relievers	Gain creators
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Because the RAiD Metadata Record is easy to maintain, it provides a stable information source for reporting <input type="checkbox"/> Information is documented in a standardized way with use of the RAiD Metadata Record <input type="checkbox"/> Information is easy to register by using a user-friendly RAiD GUI which populates the metadata in the RAiD DB <input type="checkbox"/> RAiD Metadata Record is initialized at project inception, and modified as the project continues, keeping an up-to-date source of truth <input type="checkbox"/> Information is connected across systems using the RAiD API for integration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Because RAiD provides a way to register project information throughout a project's lifespan via the RAiD GUI, information is easily available for Research Administrators, Research Infrastructure Operators, and Operators of a Research Platform <input type="checkbox"/> Because RAiD provides a single source of truth in the RAiD DB, it enables Researcher Administrators, Operators of a Research Platform, Funders and Integrators/Harvesters to manage research information quickly, without having to gather information from other sources <input type="checkbox"/> Because RAiD provides a single source of truth accompanied by a standardized RAiD Metadata Record stored in the RAiD DB, information is reliable and trustable for Research Administrators, Researchers, Research Support Staff, and Integrators/Harvesters <input type="checkbox"/> Because the RAiD API provides a connection to the RAiD Metadata Records, project information will be interoperable for other systems, like Integrators/Harvesters, but also other systems used for registering and tracking research information, like those often used by Research Administrators, Researchers/Support Staff, Funders and Operators of a Research Platform

- | | |
|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> The RAiD (system) DB becomes a single-source of truth for information, instead of information being siloed across systems | |
|---|--|

Business model

To sustain a service over time a business model is required. It helps anticipate the costs of operating the service but should also cover improving it. For the EOSC RAiD service, SURF established a business model which captures the costs of operating the service, delivered by a product manager, technical advisors, and system administrators. In addition, the business model estimated the cost for service development and improvement over time.

After many months of discussing the service with multiple departments and the management board at SURF, it was determined that the service might best be funded by a collective business model. This model would be financed by sectors — instead of individual contracts with institutes — where each of the institutes in the sectors would contribute a tariff to purchase the service together. This collective model, shared by the research-performing sectors that SURF supports, entails 73 institutes covering the operational and long-term development costs of the service. This was achieved by identifying the value of the service at an ecosystem level: By all sectors contributing to the service and getting access, it lowers the barrier to standardising open research information at the institutional level, and as a consequence, greatly matures the open research information landscape by enabling the connectivity of this information across all the institutes who collectively participate for the improvement of open science in their sectors.

Alongside this, SURF has established a Freemium service model, for individual researchers and small teams who wish to quickly get access to a free version of the RAiD service across Europe. In the long-term, if they wish to grow their RAiD operation to an institutional level, SURF will transition them to a contracted service.

When starting a new service, it is important to understand all the relevant stakeholders required to do so, besides just the typical product teams themselves who build and maintain a service. The personnel costs of running the service in the product team at SURF were estimated at a total of ~1.2FTE, which includes activities related to service delivery, technical consultation, and service administration, for both operational and development costs. While personnel costs for a new service are almost entirely related to product development, development costs continue year-over-year if there is an expectation to improve the service over time. Alongside this, resources at SURF during development were used for various activities related to strategy, product and portfolio management, and privacy and legal consultation (in relation to agreements and contracts), to name a few. Combined, these activities prepare a new service for sustainable operation and adoption. SURF advises potential Registration Agencies to take the whole service development picture into account, and to apply a rigorous lifecycle product management process to mitigate risks related to issues such as quality and budget overspend, especially since starting up such an organization necessarily entails extensive collaboration with multiple groups of stakeholders which can be subject to creeps in scope.

Pilot use cases

During service development at SURF pilots are carried out with institutions as a way not only to demonstrate the utility and value of the service, but for the service team to better understand how users will use the service, offering opportunities for feedback and learning during development. Of the many engagements with funders, medical centres, applied science colleges, universities, and research institutes where the SURF

team documented different use cases, the EOSC RAiD service team defined two specific use cases for piloting the service during development:

1. *Research institute use case*

The institute implements complex pipelines throughout their organisation for lab experiments and computing datasets. An integration of RAiD was designed where the various systems involved at different stages of these pipelines would interact with RAiD to document the resources being used and track the outputs of the various systems processing data. By so doing, the integration necessarily exploits RAiD’s versioning capabilities, where the actions taken from the systems generate new versions of the existing RAiDs. This versioning capability also supports future reproducibility efforts. Alongside this, mappings between their main information systems and RAiD were made to standardise project information within their infrastructure.

2. *University use case*

The university is developing a new information management system and is missing a key layer which allows them to integrate this new system with existing systems in their infrastructure, such as the CRIS system in use. The scope of the use case is to design their new information system. RAiD connects the various systems to one another to become a single source of truth for project information, and standardises the architecture by offering a project information data model to exploit.

While the final delivery of a production-ready service is the most tangible output of the work performed, much of the collaborative work in getting the service developed and adopted by user communities and institutes is perhaps the most valuable. At the time of this project, more institutes than not were developing - or even completely overhauling - their information architecture, and engaging them about their efforts and goals positioned RAiD for an adoption that would improve the maturity and quality of their information management for the long-term.

6 Task 4.5 Demonstrators

Task 4.5 Demonstrators

Lead: CLARIN

Participants: CSC, OPENAIRE, GWDG, DKRZ

- **Demonstrate metadata schema hosting for schema that are not already hosted by others (e.g. CESSDA’s DDI schema), and secondly demonstrates referring to externally hosted schema for communities that already have such a registry (e.g. CLARIN) but for whom registration of their metadata schema in a central EOSC registry increases their FAIRness. The registries will be seeded initially from the RDA metadata schema registry content and the metadata schema and crosswalks available from other EOSC components for bootstrapping such as EUDAT central B2SHARE.**
- **Develop a demonstrator to facilitate projects and researchers to create and share crosswalks with others that can reuse and improve them; useful a.o. for the B2FIND discovery service, providing an easy configuration and customisation mechanism of crosswalks for mapping harvested community metadata onto the generic B2FIND schema.**
- **Develop a demonstrator showcasing application of the DTR in typing metadata scheme’s elements and attributes esp. from core EOSC components as B2SHARE and the use of registered data-types and data-type converters for research data format conversion**

6.1 Introduction and background

The Demonstrator task 4.5 provides several implementations and documents that demonstrate the usefulness of the MSCR and DTR registries. Contrary to the case-studies implementations under WP7 task

7.3, the Demonstrators are conceived outside the immediate context of a specific research community and work closely with the component development teams. The Demonstrator implementations are intended to be useful beyond the "demonstrating" aspect, since the development teams usually have a good idea and lengthy experience in respect of the added value of the component and how it may serve the research communities in general.

Requirements gathering

From the GA (and esp. the T4.5 description) and discussion with various stakeholders, a number of Demonstrators were conceived that are directly specified in the FAIRCORE4EOSC project Grant Agreement (GA):

- Schema seeding demonstrator,
- B2FIND demonstrator,
- metadata schema typing,
- DTR as extended MIME-Type registry,
- B2SHARE demonstrator.

Additionally, originally unforeseen activities were specified as additional Demonstrators which can be classified as technical collaborations with external partners, or additional activities of project partners in T4.5. Some of these demonstrators have been formalised through letters of intent (LoI) or a memorandum of understanding (MoU). The external collaborations also count towards the Key Performance Indicator (KPI) #5, co-design of FAIRCORE4EOSC components by external stakeholders, through new requirements for development and feedback on the developed features.

In this way, a number of new Demonstrators were added to the original Demonstrator ideas:

- B2INST Demonstrator,
- OpenAIRE RG Demonstrator,
- SWITCH/Connectome collaboration.

From the beginning there has been a close collaboration with task T3.6 led by DKRZ concerning the methodology of the FC4E project's two demonstrator tasks, since these were seen to have a special nature compared to the community case-studies managed by task 7.1. This led to the initial creation of a number of scripts that as far as could be predicted would describe adequate user-stories and implementations for the goals for T4.5. The scripts were initially also excellent ways to exchange ideas with the MSCR and DTR development teams. During the course of the project the scripts were updated several times, when ideas about the functionality and implementations matured and changed.

The experience with using the FC4E project Jira for requirements gathering are somewhat mixed, the Jira is an excellent tool to manage software development but especially in the initial phase of the Demonstrators requirement discussion the use of video conferencing, face-to-face discussions, shared Google documents and project Wiki proved much more useful. JIRA, on the other hand, provides solid administrative task description and management functions that proved useful. It may be worthwhile to save some of the Jira ticket information e.g. user-stories and requirements in more sustainable format such as Zenodo publications.

Demonstrator creation

The Demonstrator task has one associated Milestone MS22 which reported on the state of the Demonstrators in M24. Delays with the MSCR development, which had to be built from the ground up,

prevented full realisation of all the planned demonstrators. On the positive side, several other initially unplanned Demonstrators were delivered.

In discussion with PC and PO it was decided to keep working on the unfinished Demonstrators until end of the project (M36) if resources were available, without having a formally postponed MS22 reporting obligation beyond the usual technical reporting of by the project partners. Although this lacks formal obligation of delivery, it was considered acceptable in view of flexibility and avoiding administrative complexities.

The status of the Demonstrators and the MS22 milestone reporting was discussed in the technical meeting in Athens May 23-25 2024, and the proposed priorities were agreed. See slide set [T3.6 & T4.5 B2FIND Demonstrators](#). In addition, at the EUDAT Conference in Karlsruhe, December 3-5-2024, FAIRCORE4EOSC contributions to EUDAT service development and benefits for research communities in general were presented and discussed, see the slide set [FAIRCORE4EOSC contributions to EUDAT service development](#).

6.2 The Demonstrators

6.2.1 The MSCR Seeding Demonstrator (MSCR)

The MSCR Seeding Demonstrator shows the capability of the MSCR to host & register a set of metadata schema and crosswalks taken from existing metadata schema registries such as the [FAIRsharing](#)¹⁷ and [RDA metadata standards catalogue](#)¹⁸. Choices for specific schema were based on:

- Suitable format - during the project the MSCR has extended its capability to process different types of schema.
- Availability - the metadata schema is not available as a single schema but has to be created using highly specialised tools.
- Discipline diversity - although this was limited by the available expertise, and there is some bias towards the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) disciplines.

Note that of the use of the MSCR in the different use cases managed by WP7 also tested the processing and hosting of metadata schema (e.g. CERIF related schema for the "[European Integration of National-level Services](#)" case study, (Elbers et al., 2025; Kesäniemi et al., 2024)).

The Seeding Demonstrator activities served as an essential testing process for the capabilities of the MSCR parser and provided feedback on the state of the MSCR GUI which was important with respect to especially the first-time user-experience. At the technical meeting in Athens (22-4-2024), it was reported that from 19 selected schemas, the MSCR parsed less than 50% (cross-checking also with Oxygen XML software if the schemas were correct). The UI was also improved from Seeding Demonstrator feedback. Initial priorities for the MSCR development team were mainly obtained from the WP7 community research infrastructure integration case -studies that relied mainly on the MSCR API, few use-cases entailed using the UI. Current numbers are far better, only 2 from 37 schema and crosswalk processing fail at the time of writing (9-4-2025).

The [MSCR Vocabulary Service](#) was tested by uploading and managing some SKOS vocabularies, e.g. testing its capability hosting large vocabularies (> 10k terms) and using it as a demonstration for projects

¹⁷ <https://fairsharing.org/>

¹⁸ <https://rdamsc.bath.ac.uk/>

needing a potential vocabulary service platform. The MSCR vocabulary service offers limited editing functionality, contrary to other platforms that only support publication.

Since the development process of the MSCR required sometimes purging the hosted schemas and crosswalks the process of adding and deleting metadata schema and crosswalks was automated using the MSCR API. Available are a set of scripts to quickly test the MSCR parsing and hosting functionality. The scripts, a list of tested schemas and the test results are available in GitHub¹⁹.

The difference between hosting and registering of schema and crosswalks, which was emphasised in the project description, proved to be less relevant and mainly of administrative interest (e.g. part of a crosswalk metadata), no special testing took place except requiring that metadata schema could be both uploaded from a local machine and remote server.

At the time of writing this D4.1, the MSCR has still some problems parsing some XSD and JSON schema, and adding new schema and testing will continue until end of project (May -25/M36). The MSCR development team has stated some priorities with respect to schema support and not all schema currently still failing to parse will be supported in the MSCR version resulting this project.

6.2.2 The B2FIND Demonstrator (MSCR)

The B2FIND Demonstrator aims to utilise the MSCR functionality to enhance the operational metadata ingest process of the discovery service. By creating and managing the crosswalks necessary for converting harvested community metadata into the EUDAT Core schema, B2FIND benefits in several ways:

- Simplified mapping from and to new or updated schema versions.
- Centralised maintenance and versioning of schemas and crosswalks in the MSCR,
- Different management roles allow seamless interaction with community experts, who are enabled to co-editing crosswalks associated to them and allow EUDAT managers to retrieve the updated versions to adopt and customise metadata ingestion.

The associated use case is shown in the following figure:

Figure 23: MSCR in B2FIND's metadata ingestion workflow

¹⁹ <https://github.com/clarin-eric/FAIRCORE4EOSC-T4.5/tree/main/scripts>

The demonstrator tested and evaluated this by uploading [DataCite 4.6](#) (DataCite Metadata Working Group, 2024) as source schema and [EUDAT Core 1.1](#)²⁰ as target schema, both encoded as XSD via the [MSCR user interface](#) and by creating a crosswalk from [DataCite 4.6 to EUDAT Core 1.1](#) in MSCR format.

Figure 24: Crosswalk creation panel with source and target schema

Further evaluation and use of the MSCR role concept with regard to schema updates (including the use of versioning) is ongoing work and will allow community experts to inspect and comment the crosswalks. A more detailed description of the different user and administrator roles can be found in the description of the MSCR in this report (see 3).

Figure 25: User rights management in MSCR for group administrators

The roles (see Figure 25.) allow different editing rights for crosswalks within a certain user group. This provides the basis for collaborative creation, editing and maintenance of crosswalks from standard formats to B2FIND's EUDAT Core format together with the repository managers, who are usually experts in their domain metadata standards. These community-approved crosswalks can then be found, shared and re-used by other interested data managers from one central registry. Regarding the B2FIND ingest and mapping workflow, use of MSCR eases communication with the communities and saves time and effort on creating, updating and hosting the crosswalk.

6.2.3 The metadata schema typing Demonstrator (DTR and MSCR)

The metadata schema typing Demonstrator illustrates the practical use of typing schema elements and attribute values for purposes of documentation, validation and conversion. The DTR will serve as a type registry for basic-types used in both the MSCR and DTR hosted schema. Typing is very relevant for increasing (meta-) data quality. Both MSCR and DTR should support this typing of schema elements.

²⁰ <https://schema.eudat.eu/eudatcore/>

Currently implemented are:

- A set of basic-types (info-type) for use in schema typing is registered in the DTR (see <https://typeregistry.lab.pidconsortium.net/#objects/?query=type:%22BasicInfoType%22>).
- DTR support for typing the DTR hosted schemas.
- TypeAPI to exchange type information agreed for communication with the MSCR (see <https://github.com/FC4E-T4-3/dtr-toolkit>).
- MSCR API supports editing schema data types.
- The MSCR UI to support users inspecting and editing basic-type information for MSCR hosted schemas.

Figure 26: Screenshots showing the MSCR crosswalk editor UI providing schema entity type information

6.2.4 The B2SHARE Demonstrator (DTR and MSCR)

The B2SHARE Demonstrator partly overlaps with the "[EOSC Service Providers & RDM Communities](#)" case-study (Elbers et al., 2025) and shows how both the DTR and MSCR can help operators and users of the B2SHARE repository service. For organisational reasons, the DTR was involved in managing the B2SHARE metadata schema. To manage creation of crosswalks and metadata schema evolution, this capability should also be available in the MSCR.

Currently implemented are:

- The availability of the core metadata schema used by B2SHARE (<https://typeregistry.lab.pidconsortium.net/#objects/21.T11969/f67c4f7359d2a211fb80>) and the B2SHARE core schema community extensions (such as for the [FMI community²¹](https://typeregistry.lab.pidconsortium.net/#objects/21.T11969/c92f7b96334fcddb15c5)) in the DTR (<https://typeregistry.lab.pidconsortium.net/#objects/21.T11969/c92f7b96334fcddb15c5>) and (partially) the MSCR hosted EUDAT extended schema (21.13101/EOSC-202504000311132). This includes typing information of the metadata field values.
- The functionality to export the B2SHARE metadata schema from the DTR and to import it in the MSCR (with source-code at <https://github.com/EUDAT-B2SHARE/tacos-cli>).

Some plans could not be realised and are expected to be in B2SHARE version 3 such as:

- Functionality to visualise and manage the metadata schema type information from the MSCR, and (depending on available operationalisation facilities in MSCR) based on the created crosswalks enable actual metadata conversion.

Figure 27: EUDAT service connections to FAIRCORE4EOSC services

6.2.5 The B2Inst Demonstrator (DTR)

The B2INST service provides a community-driven solution for the unique and global identification of scientific instruments (the B2INST service can be accessed via <https://b2inst.gwdg.de/>). Users can persistently reference these identifiers in other services and publications. The system is open to anyone interested in instrument registration. This Demonstrator work is in-line with the LoL - Letter of Intent signed with the PIDINST Future Initiative.

The work done in the context of the B2Inst demonstrator implemented is:

²¹ <https://fmi.b2share.csc.fi/communities/FMI>

- Community-Driven Schema Customization: Communities can now define and modify their own metadata schemas directly in the DTR, building on the default [PIDINST root schema](#)²² of B2INST to include additional information for their instruments.
- B2INST now also monitors the DTR via the DTR TypeAPI (see <https://github.com/FC4E-T4-3/dtr-toolkit>) for updates in the metadata, allowing a workflow that automatically relays any detected changes to B2INST administrators, improving promptness and integration efficiency by eliminating previous communication and time delays in metadata definition in JSON.
- Some further promotional activity and first contact with work ongoing in the [OSTrails project](#)²³ considering extensions for scientific instruments to the [Scholarly Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework \(SKG-IF\)](#).

Figure 28: DTR and B2INST integration

6.2.6 The use of the DTR as a registry for extended MIME-Types (DTR)

This demonstrator uses the DTR as a registry for extended mime-types, offering instances and complexity beyond the IANA MIME-Type registry information. The possibility to structure the MIME-Types as part of a taxonomy, and adding aliases to MIME-Types that should both be useful for use in picklists for human users. The issuing of PIDs for every extended MIME-Type is also an important step forward. Additionally, a special taxonomy facet was added to the query builder to support using the taxonomy feature of extended MIME-Types.

Extended MIME-Types have been identified as useful in the [SSH case-study](#)²⁴ (Elbers et al., 2025) and the B2SHARE demonstrator. Beyond the FAIRCORE4EOSC project there are potential important applications in creating service and tool registries, and building FAIR Digital Object infrastructure.

All MIME-Types from the IANA registry were imported in the DTR and issued a PID²⁵. Two of the extended MIME-Types were enriched with additional information as a demonstration and for later use in the SSH case-study: [text/x-cmdi-xml](#), and [text/x-tei-xml](#) extended MIME-Types.

²² <https://typeregistry.lab.pidconsortium.net/>

²³ <https://ostrails.eu/>

²⁴ <https://faircore4eosc.eu/case-studies/social-sciences-humanities>

²⁵ <https://typeregistry.lab.pidconsortium.net/#objects/21.T11969/0acb62608006dbbbcf88>

Figure 29: The text/x-cmdi-xml extended MIME Type [3] and its taxonomic relations with text/xml mime-type and the CSD metadata profile used by CLARIN CMDI

6.2.7 The OpenAIRE Demonstrator

The OpenAIRE Demonstrator is OpenAIRE's idea and contribution benefitting the project and existing OpenAIRE infrastructure. OpenAIRE is a metadata service provider and harvests large numbers of metadata records from different affiliate metadata providers using various metadata schemas. Maintaining many transformation scripts is not feasible and scalable in the long run, and OpenAIRE has introduced its own metadata schema i.e. OpenAIRE Guidelines.

This demonstrator investigated possibilities of using the MSCR, to define and share crosswalks from known standards (e.g. Dublin Core, DataCite, CERIF), widely adopted and supported by many scholarly institutional repositories, and the OpenAIRE Guidelines based schemas. The OpenAIRE Graph metadata curators, as well as any other provider of Scholarly Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) or aggregators, could benefit from the adoption of the MSCR as part of the aggregation methodologies, by involving data source managers as an actor of the process. Crosswalks from data source standard (or proprietary) formats to other formats could this way be collaboratively maintained by data source managers, SKG and aggregator providers, and the community as a whole, ensuring up-to-date expert-defined mappings that are transparently maintained.

The demonstrator encompasses a:

- Guide explaining context and creation of a cross-walk from DublinCore (DC) to OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repositories v4 (Manghi & Shah, 2024)
- Using the MSCR, communities can benefit by creating a crosswalk between their datasource's metadata schema and OpenAIRE Guidelines v4. This example crosswalk will guide and facilitate their process of making their metadata schema compatible with OpenAIRE Guidelines v4²⁶. Some of the schema involved "datacite-v4" and "Dublin Core" have been successfully registered at the MSCR. Additional community schema and the crosswalks themselves still need to be worked on.

Every month, the OpenAIRE PROVIDE management team are hosting a webconference call²⁷ with the OpenAIRE content providers community. In the community call on May 14, 2025, a presentation about an

²⁶ <https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

²⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/provide-community-calls>

introduction to MSCR was delivered to the community. Participants showed keen interest in the features of the tool.

Figure 30: OpenAIRE communities using the MSCR to create crosswalks from community schema to the OpenAIRE guidelines

From the report several recommendations were made to the MSCR development team. Some concerning improvements for the UI, shared access for co-creation, but also a number that have bearing on the MSCR use for instruction and training of community metadata experts/data stewards.

- Providing shared access to crosswalks for crosswalk co-creation
- For instruction and documentation purposes provide ways to add additional information to metadata schema
- Provisioning supplementary information - Allow users to provide and share any material that could become handy to third-party willing to implement a given crosswalk: software libraries in GitHub, XSLTs, test data, documentation, etc.; This could be in the form of uploading files or providing comments and URL links
- Users need to be able to associate a field-to-field mapping that involves a source and target vocabulary with a function that specifies the terms-to-term (many to one) map between the two; ideally, users should be able to manage such a map from the crosswalk editing UI, although the map could be an object on its own, to be shared (or co-edited) with other users. Deep integration with the DTR service and/or SKOS systems could be a solution.
- Known consumers of the crosswalks are also implementers of the crosswalks in their own applications and would certainly wish to be notified of any changes that may occur, so as to reflect the change in their code

Some of these recommendations overlap with the requirements from other Demonstrators and case-studies such as functionality for shared access and co-creation, others are unique but should be considered important in view of future ambitions for the MSCR i.e. serving communities as an information source for sharing expert knowledge.

6.2.8 Collaboration with SWITCH/CONNECTOME project

As an implementation of the *Letter of Intent to Collaborate*, signed 12/2023 between the Swiss NREN Switch²⁸ and FAIRCORE4EOSC, a technical collaboration with Switch was started. No specific goals were formulated for the MS22 milestone at M24. Switch creates a Swiss metadata harvester for research information/products and needs to address the challenge of mapping all harvested metadata in a central DB using the RDF Mapping Language RML. A proof of concept demonstrating the conversion of MSCR crosswalks into RML mappings was developed in two iterations. The first iteration showcased the conversion from the OpenAlex JSON schema²⁹ to Switch SHACL shapes describing a subset of schema.org³⁰ as an RML mapping generated from an MSCR crosswalk. The results of the first iteration were presented at pre-day event of EuroCRIS Paris (26-11-2024) and at the conference "Knowledge Graphs for Data Integration" in Ghent (10-12-2024)³¹.

The code used to generate the RML in the first phase was part of the MSCR code base and closely related to MSCR implementation details, which is not ideal for reusability. In the second iteration, a new repository³² was created with the idea of creating a version of the RML generator that would be easier to use as a standalone library. The first version of the MSCR-RML generator was finished with test cases for different serialization formats such as JSON and XML. The use of RML functions remains a challenge since there is still no standard set of functions implemented by available RML engines.

6.3 Remaining Demonstrator Ideas

The Demonstrator task provided additional opportunities for open meetings to discuss the many potential uses of the emerging MSCR and DTR services beyond those directly stipulated by the project. In the end many of those use cases do not seem worth mentioning anymore. Some of the ideas raised in those discussions are worth mentioning, either because they are low-hanging fruit, or should be further discussed and may be realised as part of a new project.

Vocabulary merging using the MSCR

The idea for using MSCR for merging two or more vocabularies as one single new vocabulary comes from discussions in the SSH Vocabulary Commons, a network from the SSH Cluster (SSHOC) (Broeder & Odijk, 2024). In the SSH cluster the DARIAH and CLARIN infrastructures collaborate creating and using the same tools, however the scope of DARIAH is the broad Humanities, while CLARIN is more focused on Language resources and Language technology. For classification and metadata purposes DARIAH uses the TaDiRAH vocabulary³³: while CLARIN has CSD-TT³⁴ which is more detailed. Both are in the SKOS format.

- There is a desire to use a combined / merged vocabulary for some tools i.e. metadating and searching while keeping two separate domains of (editorial) responsibility
- There are relations between concepts from both vocabularies to be made

²⁸ <https://www.switch.ch/en>

²⁹ <https://help.openalex.org/hc/en-us/articles/24396686889751-About-us>

³⁰ <http://schema.org/>

³¹ <https://u0152642.pages.gitlab.kuleuven.be/kg4di-fwo-network/resources/Gent-presentations/2024-12-10-presentation-1-switch.pdf>

³² <https://github.com/CSCfi/mscr-rmlgenerator>

³³ <https://vocabs.dariah.eu/tadirah/en/>

³⁴ <https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/csd-tool-tasks/en/>

- The need to create (just in time) a merged vocabulary from the latest version of TaDiRAH and CSD ToolTask

The MSCR Vocabulary Service can help, (1) creating the relations between TaDiRAH and CSD-TT concepts and (2) subsequently creating a new merged SKOS file that contains the two original vocabularies and the newly created mappings.

6.4 Conclusions

Although it was not foreseen in the project planning, the Demonstrator task has functioned as a flexible platform to discuss new ideas and options with respect to the use and development of MSCR and DTR, including aspects of their future sustainability and looking beyond the confines of the project. The many ideas that were discussed could not all be addressed in the form of actual implementation and co-creation, but they hopefully remain embedded in the network of the respective component development teams.

7 WP4 Services EOSC Integration: GRNET and CYFRONET

7.1 EOSC integration

One of the tasks for WP4 was the analysis and design of the integration with EOSC-Core services. The integration with EOSC-Core services during the project period was conducted in two distinct phases. **Phase 1** took place while EOSC-Core services were managed by the EOSC-Future project. **Phase 2** commenced following the conclusion of EOSC-Future and the subsequent transfer of pilot integration activities to the EOSC-Core Innovation Sandbox, operated under EOSC-Beyond. Unfortunately, there was a six-month gap between the two phases, with Phase 1 ending on 15 April 2024 and Phase 2 beginning in October 2024.

At the beginning of the project, the EOSC-Core services were managed by the EOSC-Future project. Unfortunately, during the project, the plans changed with the handover to the EOSC EU NODE. The EOSC Providers Portal and the EOSC Catalogue & Marketplace as operated by EOSC Future were phased out as of 15 April 2024. The rest of the Services were phased out and replaced after a few months by their equivalents operated by the EOSC EU Node operators. Full features of the EOSC EU Node went live in the second half of 2024.

The EOSC EU node however was governed by different policies and procedures, which at that point were not available and it was expected to be focused on delivering production-managed services rather than acting as an incubator/sandbox. The evolution of the current EOSC Core component and their adaptation to become compatible with the new EOSC Federation model was expected to be continued by the EOSC Beyond Project. The EOSC Beyond project offers the EOSC Core innovation sandbox which offers the possibility to pilot integrations with the state-of-the-art EOSC Core components and services. FAIRCORE4EOSC will therefore focus its integration with the core platform by making use of the EOSC Core innovation sandbox when it becomes available as this will help to expedite the process. The EOSC Association is in the process of establishing the opportunity areas for a number of subjects including EOSC Core and FAIRCORE4EOSC is one of the projects invited to contribute with its feedback on how the EOSC Architecture can be improved and extended in the future.

Based on these, transitioning between the two environments proved challenging, primarily due to differences in service deployment policies and objectives. While the services under EOSC-Future were treated as production-grade with full support, the EOSC-Core Innovation Sandbox is designed as a testbed for evaluating technical integrations.

GRNET and Cyfronet acted as liaisons to EOSC Beyond project in order for FAIRCORE4EOSC to be handled with top-priority when the EOSC Core innovation sandbox was inaugurated and pushed for its inauguration to be moved forward so as to allow for more time to integrate FAIRCORE4EOSC in the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox. Furthermore, it was GRNET that issued a clear statement (see below) describing the need to switch focus to EOSC Beyond Core Innovation Sandbox early enough. Specifically for WP4, GRNET and Cyfronet supported the integration of WP4s service in both phases by offering know-how in their respective areas of expertise, guidance and support. They also presented the integration options in a number of workshops described below.

7.1.1 Workshops and interactions with FAIRCORE4EOSC Services

GRNET and Cyfronet have participated actively in all TSGs and all-hands meetings of FAIRCORE4EOSC and provided updates on the current status of EOSC Core services for both Phase 1 and 2.

Throughout the project, a series of workshops and dedicated meetings were held, focusing on the integration of the FAIRCORE4EOSC core components. These sessions provided valuable opportunities for technical alignment, discussion of implementation details, and clarification of integration pathways.

Following each workshop, the development teams continued their efforts by conducting further testing and experimentation with the necessary capabilities. This ongoing work was essential for assessing compatibility and making progress toward successful integration with the EOSC-Core components.

Below is a summary of some key workshops and interactions that took place during the project.

15 March 2023, Online - RAiD and EOSC- Core Services

GRNET and Cyfronet, along with participants from the EOSC-Future project and in collaboration with the RAiD project, organized an online workshop to introduce the EOSC-Core components and the broader EOSC ecosystem during the first phase of the project. The workshop served as a foundational session for RAiD stakeholders, providing them with key insights into the technical and procedural aspects of integrating with the EOSC platform. One of the main goals of the session was to help participants understand the overall onboarding process and to outline the technical steps required for successful alignment with EOSC services. By the end of the session, attendees were expected to have a clearer understanding of the next actions to be taken from the FC4E side. The first part of the presentation was dedicated to introducing essential EOSC terminology through the "EOSC Terms 101" segment, followed by an overview of the EOSC Architecture. It also focused on introducing key EOSC-Core components, particularly AAI, EOSC Catalogue and Marketplace, Helpdesk, and Monitoring. In addition to the functional overview of these components, the session also introduced the relevant interoperability guidelines that ensure seamless integration and compliance across services.

April 2024, Series of workshops, Online

In order to foster and support further the integration of FAIRCORE4EOSC components with EOSC Core, a series of dedicated workshops were scheduled for April 2024. These workshops aimed to familiarise developers of each component with each EOSC Core component and the corresponding interoperability guidelines to make use of them. The topics of these workshops were:

- Connecting to the EOSC Core Infrastructure Proxy, or joining the EOSC AAI Federation/eduGAIN
- Have your service monitored through the EOSC Monitoring service
- How to publish service and research product accounting figures in EOSC
- Integrate with the EOSC Helpdesk
- Make your research products discoverable in EOSC

- Onboard your service into the EOSC Exchange

4-5 December 2024

FAIRCORE4EOSC organised a workshop between both projects at the EUDAT Conference on the 4-5 December 2024, Karlsruhe, Germany. The workshop was organised as a one day workshop, spread across two days. After introductory presentations from EOSC Beyond and FAIRCORE4EOSC projects, to learn the main aims and scope of the projects, a deep dive session was organised to learn about the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox components and integration options. The majority of interest centred around Federated AAI, Monitoring, and Helpdesk functionalities. As a result, the hands-on session primarily focused on the integration of these specific components with the corresponding Sandbox environments.

7.1.2 Integration with Components

EOSC Core AAI

One of the main interests of the components was the Federated AAI. The FC4E services—Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry (MSCR), EOSC-Data Type Registry, and Research Artifact ID (RAID)—were originally integrated with the Demo environment of the EOSC Portal AAI to enable seamless user authentication and access. Following the decommissioning of the EOSC Portal AAI (operated in the context of EOSC Future), these services were migrated to the EOSC Sandbox AAI to maintain functionality and ensure alignment with the evolving EOSC ecosystem. GRNET supported and guided the services in order to facilitate this transition.

The connection to the Innovation Sandbox has been facilitated through the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox Service Registry³⁵. This integration follows the guidelines outlined in the documentation³⁶. For MSCR and EOSC-Data Type Registry, this setup allows users to log in with different credentials supported by the EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox AAI, including the academic identity providers available through the eduGAIN interederation³⁷, EU Login³⁸, and eIDAS.

However, for RAID, despite specific guidance provided to enable its connection to the EOSC Sandbox AAI and the Innovation Sandbox, the service has not yet been successfully connected. The guidance adhered to the same integration process outlined in the documentation, targeting connectivity through the EOSC Federated AAI.

EOSC Core Monitoring

The EOSC Monitoring was another service that was integrated by the EOSC-Core components. The EOSC Monitoring is offering levels like the Base Monitoring and the User Perspective Monitoring.

The Base Monitoring provides essential base monitoring through simple health checks to ensure that services are responsive and alive. It offers real-time alerting and detailed reporting, enhancing the overall observability of service status. This step is done by default when a service decides to be added into the Monitoring Service. The User Perspective Monitoring goes beyond basic health checks by evaluating the service from the end-user's point of view, adding extra business value based on its core functionalities. It verifies critical user interactions such as the ability to log in and successfully download files. This approach provides better trends, deeper insights, and a clearer understanding of how real users experience the

³⁵ accessible at <https://core-proxy.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/federation/>

³⁶ <https://docs.sandbox.eosc-beyond.eu/Service%20Portfolio/AAI/AAI/>

³⁷ <https://edugain.org/>

³⁸ https://trusted-digital-identity.europa.eu/index_en

service. As a result, it supports improved decision-making, enhances service quality, and ultimately increases user satisfaction.

The process of integrating the Faircore4EOSC components to the EOSC Monitoring was expanded in both phases. In order to validate the integration with the EOSC innovation sandbox, all the FAIRCORE4EOSC components, services were added to the Monitoring service by GRNET³⁹ and the Base monitoring started. MSCR and DTR were interested in continuing in the User Perspective Monitoring.

EOSC Core Helpdesk

The Helpdesk within the EOSC ecosystem is an integral component that plays a pivotal role in maintaining seamless service delivery. It facilitates real-time communication, allowing EOSC customers and users to quickly resolve issues and access necessary support. By providing proactive assistance, the Helpdesk helps anticipate and address potential challenges before they impact service availability. This ensures the continuous and stable operation of EOSC services. Furthermore, it acts as a key resource for service providers and research communities, offering guidance, troubleshooting, and ensuring that their needs are met efficiently. Ultimately, the Helpdesk enhances the overall user experience and contributes to the reliability and success of the EOSC ecosystem. GRNET facilitated the integration with EOSC Helpdesk. Currently RAiD is finalizing the Integration with Helpdesk in the EOSC Beyond innovation sandbox.

EOSC Service Catalogue and Marketplace

The EOSC Service Catalogue and Marketplace in the EOSC ecosystem during Phase 1 served as the main component responsible for managing services onboarded to EOSC and their exposure to users. Upon the transition to Phase 2, where EOSC evolved into a federation of nodes, the fundamental concept remained unchanged. However, the model has shifted. It remains true that EOSC will feature tools responsible for service management and service discovery and access for users. Instead of a single EOSC Service Catalogue and Marketplace, the EOSC Federation of Nodes will implement a Service Discovery and Access Capability, facilitated by various tools similar to the existing (and integrated) EOSC Service Catalogue and Marketplace found within the Federation.

This change necessitated a new strategy for exposing FC4E components and an understanding of where the services could achieve visibility within EOSC. Cyfronet and GRNET actively participated in project-level discussions on how to navigate this new model in EOSC. After consensus was reached, Cyfronet supported FC4E services (from WP3 and WP4) in onboarding to the EOSC Beyond's ecosystem (EOSC Core Innovation Sandbox).

Moreover, at the proposal stage of the FC4E project, it was decided that the EOSC Marketplace (a component of the EOSC Service Catalogue and Marketplace) would be utilized to expose the functionalities of RAIDs within the EOSC ecosystem. A dedicated development effort was undertaken to achieve this, as presented in the chapter devoted to T4.4.

Following the transition from Phase 1 to Phase 2, the technology implementing the EOSC Marketplace was transferred to the EOSC Beyond project to establish a reference technology for the EOSC Nodes. This will enable the support and exposure of the Service Discovery and Access Capability in an EOSC-interoperable manner. The implementation of RAIDs was completed in this context, and now, with the Marketplace being one of the services offered as a technology for EOSC Nodes, there is potential for its adoption by the nodes.

³⁹ <https://ui.devel.mon.argo.grnet.gr/beyond>

Lastly, regarding the Service Discovery and Access Capability in EOSC, Cyfronet has investigated the possibility of the Data Type Registry (DTR) becoming a core service in EOSC, responsible for the maintenance of EOSC Profiles⁴⁰. The DTR will act as a component connecting to other core components within EOSC that utilize these profiles (similar to how the service profile is utilized in the EOSC Marketplace). Following a positive assessment, this concept was presented to project partners and followed with a lightweight proof-of-concept activity. The DTR team is currently implementing the provider and service profile schemas in the DTR to verify DTR's accuracy and applicability for this initiative.

8 Summary and conclusions

The time span for the service development in FAIRCORE4EOSC was challenging. Getting the development teams working and a full spectrum of specifications by project month 8 was intensive. Having 10 months to develop the beta releases was even tougher. This was a necessary and planned step to allow for enough time for the case studies to adopt the work during the lifetime of the project. This turned out to be more challenging than thought, as the beta versions with limited functionality were not in all cases adequate to satisfy the more complex use cases of the case studies. The service development teams were then working with the case studies during the next 16 months to prioritise and ensure that the development efforts toward the final releases of the services fulfilled the case study and other stakeholders needs. The project had an overall KPI for satisfying at least 80% of the accepted user requirements (for all services), and this KPI was met. The requirements were consistently monitored and refined as the implementation work progressed. Follow up of the progress in meeting the requirements was a recurring point on the agenda of project meetings.

“In general, the FAIRCORE4EOSC project has planned to produce services, addressing gaps in FAIR according to the SRIA v1.0. The services that the project has developed are now produced and launched, and carry added value in advancing FAIR even if they would not be EOSC services in future by definition. Thus, the main contribution of the project to the future of the EOSC partnership is indeed the services that have been developed in the course of the project.” (Halonen et al., 2025) This deliverable serves to provide a technical account of the development work and the three services developed in work package 4: MSCR, DTR and RAiD. This deliverable also gives context for the work by showcasing the requirement collection and progress monitoring work. Finally, the demonstrators have shown the practical application context for the developed services. The deliverable draws out the full picture and provides more detail than is possible to give in a typical scientific paper, and the authors hope that this can serve as a point of reference in the future, for the work carried out in FAIRCORE4EOSC project.

Significant effort also went into disseminating the development work (Halonen et al., 2025). For the first 18 months the communication was related to aligning efforts between different EOSC and non EOSC-actors, talking essentially about what was planned to be done. This served to raise interest in adoption. After the release of the beta versions, the focus gradually shifted to showcasing the developed services. Especially for the MSCR, users are lining up, showcasing the real need for the service in the science communities.

⁴⁰ <https://eosc-profiles.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

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Appendix I. Different MSCR schema visualisations

The basic tree structure that materialises all the possible nodes is used for CSV, JSON schema, XSD and SKOS schemas (Appendix I. Figure 1.).

Appendix I. Figure 1. Basic tree structure view of a schema

SHACL and RDFS schemas are visualised using a tree where the root contains classes referenced in the schema with associated (either with sh:property of rdfs:domain) properties as child elements (Appendix I. Figure 2.).

Appendix I. Figure 2. SHACL and RDFS schema tree view

SKOS and ENUM vocabularies show the full hierarchy (See Appendix I. Figure 3.)

Appendix I. Figure 3. SHACL and RDFS schema tree view

OWL ontologies have a special representation that divides the tree into classes, data properties and object properties (see Appendix I. Figure 4.).

Appendix I. Figure 4. OWL ontology tree

When a user selects a node from the tree a detailed node info box is shown on the right-hand side (see figure X) containing all the information that was extracted from the schema specification file. The actual content is again dependent on the schema format. For example, it is not possible to provide a description of a column within a CSV schema, because the only piece of information available is the name of the field.

Appendix I. Figure 5. Node info

Search from schema		Selected node info	
<input type="text" value="Find an attribute..."/>			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▼ resource > identifier > creators > titles <ul style="list-style-type: none"> publisher publicationYear > resourceType > subjects > contributors > dates language > alternateIdentifiers > relatedIdentifiers 	<pre> type: object title: resource description: Root element of a single record. This wrapper element is for XML implementation only and is not defined in the DataCite DOI standard. Note: This is the case for all wrapper elements within this schema.No content in this wrapper element. maxCount: 1 minCount: 1 namespace: http://datacite.org/schema/kernel-4 </pre>		

Appendix II. Mapping example: DataCite XML to schema.org RDF

This section demonstrates some of the key mappings features of the MSCR using two common schemas: DataCite v4.4 and schema.org. The crosswalk used in the example comes from the "DataCite Metadata Schema 4.4 to [Schema.org](https://schema.org) Mapping" document published by Datacite in 2022 (<https://zenodo.org/records/7661399>). The example is based on the assumptions that the source schema is registered using the DataCite 4.4 XSD available at <https://doi.org/10.14454/fxws-0523> and the target is registered with a SHACL version of the schema.org from TopQuadrant (<https://datashapes.org/schema>). The SHACL version of the schema.org is used because the purpose of this example crosswalk is to transform data.

The source instance document used for the example is available through the same DOI as the schema itself ([example with DataCollector as Contributor and a geoLocation box](#)). In order to keep the example concise, only subset of the source elements are included in the example. The target schema.org document (expressed in JSON-LD) is shown in Listing X. @id fields with example values are added to the author, spatialCoverage and geo objects because blank RDF nodes are not yet supported.

```
{
  "@id": "http://doi.org/10.5072/DataCollector_dateCollected_geoLocationBox",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "name": "Temperature and Humidity in School Classrooms, Ponhook Lake, N.S.,
1961-1962",
  "author": [
    {
      "@id": "id:1",
      "@type": "Person",
      "name": "Peach, A."
    }
  ],
  "inLanguage": "en",
  "spatialCoverage": [
    {
      "@id": "id:2",
      "@type": "Place",
      "address": "Ponhook Lake, Nova Scotia",
      "geo": {
        "@id": "id:3",
        "@type": "GeoShape",
        "box": "44.7167,-64.2 44.9667,-63.8"
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Code block 5 Target document instance (JSON-LD)

RDF specific mappings

In the case of a data schema mapping where the target schema is of SHACL format i.e. the target document is an RDF graph, two additional mappings are required for each mapped target class. First, an iterator that provides the source instance data for the class instances must be mapped. Currently MSCR only supports one iterator per class. An iterator source can be any single element from the source schema. The minimum and maximum cardinalities of the source property determine the number of target class instances that can be created. The other required extra mapping provides source data for creating URIs for the class instances. The source property of this "subject source" mapping should be a property that is nested under the source of the related iterator property. Generating blank nodes is not yet supported, so each mapped class must have both iterator and subject sources mappings.

In the example, three different classes need to be mapped: schema:Dataset, schema:Person and schema:Place. Since the Dataset class is the only one with a proper identifier (DOI) it's used as an example.

The Iterator mapping is created with the following requirement: An instance of a schema:Dataset class must be generated for each "resource" element in the source document. A mapping that achieves this is shown in Appendix II. Figure 1.

Appendix II. Figure 1. Iterator mapping from root element of the DataCite schema to the iterator source of the schema:Dataset class.

The value of the resource/identifier element is used as is as the subject URI for the resource of type schema:Dataset. It can be seen from Figure Appendix II. Figure 2. that the minimum and maximum cardinality of the identifier element is 1, so it is required and non-repeatable.

Appendix II. Figure 2. Details of the identifier element.

These mappings create the triple `<http://doi.org/10.5072/DataCollector_dateCollected_geoLocationBox> rdf:type schema:Dataset` in the output graph.

Simple mapping

"language" → "inLanguage"

Adding a simple one-to-one mapping using a source property that is an immediate child of the iterator property is very straightforward. The user selects exactly one source and one target property and creates a mapping without any extra configuration (Appendix II. Figure 3.).

Appendix II. Figure 3. Simple one-to-one mapping from language to inLanguage

Iterator mapping with filter function

Person class iterator

Next a mapping is added to create instances of the schema:Person class. It is not enough to use the repeatable "creator" as the source property, because DataCite creator names can be both personal and organisational. The distinction between the two can be made by checking the value of the nameType attribute of the personName element (see Appendix II. Figure 4.). Since the author target property is to be populated, only the creator element of type "personal" must be included in the iterator.

Appendix II. Figure 4. Datacite creatorType attribute.

This is achieved using a many-to-one mapping and a filter function. Both creator and nameType elements are selected on the source side and mapped to the Person class' iterator source. Then a mapping processing called "filter" is applied with "property" and "value" parameters "nameType" and "Organisational" respectively. This effectively filters in only those creator elements that which have the desired value in the nameType attribute of the creatorName child element (see Appendix II. Figure 5.).

Appendix II. Figure 5. Many to one iterator mapping with filter function

Mapping object properties

A triple with a predicate of the type owl:ObjectProperty connects two URIs (or blank nodes, or blank nodes and a URI). Following on from the example in the section above, there is a need to create a mapping that creates the triple <Dataset> schema:author <Person>. This can be achieved by adding a mapping from the element that was used as an iterator (with or without a filter) to the class that will be the type of the object resources (see Figure Appendix II. Figure 6.). An explicit mapping is required because an object property could allow for multiple different target types. For example, the schema:author property can have both schema:Person and schema:Organization resource types as its object. The MSCR will use the iterator source mapping to infer the required object URI as part of the RML generation. It should be noted that if the same iterator source property is used in multiple object property mappings, all of these properties will have the same URIs as objects. This is due to the fact that each class can have only one iterator mapping.

Appendix II. Figure 6. Mapping object properties

Value functions

geoLocationBox → box

The final example mapping uses a many-to-one mapping with two different functions to first concatenate values of the four input properties with commas and then replace the middle comma with a space (Appendix II. Figure 7.). The "concat" mapping function takes the four separate coordinate elements as an input and produces a string "44.7167,-64.2,44.9667,-63.8". It is imperative that the numbers are in a specific order in the value of the schema:box property, so arrows next to the source properties can be used to sort them correctly. Next, a target operation, "replaceGroup" applied to the output of the mapping operation. This

function uses a regular expression to extract part of the input value and replaces it with the given "replacement" value (a single whitespace character in this case). The output of the operation ("44.7167,-64.2 44.9667,-63.8") is correctly formatted string for the schema:box property. See figure X for example of the mapping configuration in the MSCR UI.

Appendix II. Figure 7. Mapping with a concatenation operation.

Add mapping

Sources	Mapping operation	Target
<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> + southBoundLatitude </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> + westBoundLongitude </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> + northBoundLatitude </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> + eastBoundLongitude </div>	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> concat </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> delimiter , </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> Predicate Exact match </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> Notes No notes set. Add free form notes here. </div>	<div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> box </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> Type: Description: A box is the area enclosed by the rectangle formed by two points. The first point is the lower corner, the second point is the upper corner. A box is expressed as two points separated by a space character. </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> Target operation replaceGroup </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"> regex -?\d+\.\d+,-?\d+\.\d+(,) </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"> replacement </div>